

ABSTRACT

This descriptive cross-sectional study assessed the use of non-pharmacological pain management techniques among nurses at a tertiary healthcare institution. Non-pharmacological interventions are increasingly recognized as essential components of comprehensive pain management, complementing pharmacological treatments to provide holistic care. The study aimed to evaluate the frequency of use, types of techniques implemented, and the factors influencing nurses' choices of non-pharmacological methods. A proportional purposive sampling technique was used to select 130 nurses, who were then surveyed using a structured questionnaire. Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. Results showed that 64.3% of nurses regularly employed non-pharmacological pain management strategies, with reassurance and emotional support (81.4%), massage (79.1%), and patient education and counseling (76.0%) as the most frequently utilized methods. Additionally, hot/cold compress therapy (73.6%), deep breathing exercises (68.2%), and patient repositioning (69.8%) were common practices. Factors influencing these choices included institutional policies (72.9%), workload (72.1%), and specialized training in non-pharmacological techniques (69.0%). Nurses' beliefs (65.9%), time constraints (63.6%), and patient preferences (61.2%) also had significant impacts on their choices. Younger nurses with higher educational qualifications demonstrated greater utilization of these interventions, suggesting that age and education may positively impact the adoption of non-pharmacological techniques. The study highlights that while non-pharmacological pain management methods are widely used by 76.7% of nurses, various institutional and personal factors influence their implementation. To enhance non-pharmacological pain relief practices, it is recommended that healthcare institutions provide specialized training and create supportive policies to reduce workload barriers. Additionally, incorporating patient preferences into care plans could strengthen the therapeutic impact of these interventions. Future research should explore the long-term effectiveness of non-pharmacological pain management methods and examine strategies to address barriers that limit their use in diverse healthcare settings.

Keywords: Non-pharmacological measures, Relief, Patients' pain, Nurses, Tertiary health institution

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Patients in healthcare settings usually experience pain at different points in time and in different subsectors in the healthcare facility also based on an array of diverse health conditions they may be having. Regardless of the subsectors such as medical sector, surgical sectors, labour units, amongst others, these patients' pain are never a pleasant experience for them and nurses are at the forefront in helping them with relief from this pain since the nurse spends more time with the patients than any other health care professionals in the healthcare facility (Emuobor, 2024).

And a common way we generally relieve pain is with medications. Most of the time, when people experience pain, the first thing that comes to mind (be it at home or in a hospital), is the utilization of medications for attaining relief from the pain, such as Panadol, Acetaminophen, Morphine, Pentazocine, Ibuprofen, Diclofenac, Aspirin and other common analgesics. These medications may be either self administered at home or by a nurse in the healthcare facility (Emuobor, 2024).

But what if this pain stimulus could be relieved by other measures other than by the sole utilization of medications? Regardless of whether it is from home or in the healthcare facility, what if there were other means of managing pain other than fully depending on drugs?

And truly and fortunately, there are; these are what are known as the Non- Pharmaceutical Measures in the relief of patients' pain. And in this study we will be focusing on how these non pharmaceutical measures of pain relief are utilized in a particular tertiary health institution (specifically in the University Of Benin Teaching Hospital .

Meanwhile what are some common examples of non pharmaceutical measures of pain relief people commonly utilize both at home and in the hospital or other health care facility? Some common methods of nonpharmacological pain management include physical interventions such as touch, massage, hot and cold compression, positioning, acupressure, and acupuncture and psychological interventions such as cognitive behavioral therapy, breathing, meditation, relaxation, guided imagery, and hypnosis, along with other approaches such as spirituality, religion-based and music therapies. These approaches are cost-effective, evidence-based, and offer the added benefits of being easy to implement and having minimal side effects. However, effective and safe application can be a significant challenge in some health-care settings (Alrimali et al, 2023).

Therefore, are these measures actually being utilized by nurses in the tertiary health institution? Be it in conjunction with the use of medications or alone. The types commonly utilized, their utilization and even the factors that influence the choice of various methods used by nurses are all issues that drive the course of this research work and taking the University of Benin Teaching Hospital as the case study here, these questions hope to be answered (Emuobor, 2024).

1.2 Context of the Study

This study explores the application of nonpharmacological (non-drug) methods by nurses in a tertiary health institution, assessing their effectiveness, the extent of their use, barriers to nurses' effective utilization and the factors influencing nurses' choices in integrating these techniques into patient care. This research highlights the importance of these approaches, particularly in reducing reliance on medications, drug tolerance and dependency and improving patient comfort and satisfaction (Bayoumi, Khonji & Gabr 2021), as well as identifying possible new

nonpharmacological techniques that nurses can implement in relieving patients' pain using the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, Egor local government Area, Edo State, Nigeria.

1.3 STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Nurses, often the first contact for patients in pain, play a vital role in pain management, assuming various roles from pain evaluation, patient education, and treatment planning to implementation and monitoring. Florence Nightingale's historical work introduced nonpharmacological interventions such as heat, massage, music, and touch as part of her holistic approach to care. However, previous research has identified several barriers that may prevent nurses from providing nonpharmacological pain management to patients, including a lack of knowledge, time constraints, fatigue, high workload, and patient resistance (Alrimali et al, 2023).

But based on my experience during my clinicals, I observed that little to none of these non pharmaceutical measures of pain relief were utilized by nurses in UBTH in the wards I worked in, specifically those mentioned in the context of the study. This is because the nurses I worked with majorly relied on medication administration to relieve pain in patients and this was not the case at all times since the administration of medications cannot just be on demand due to the frequency of pain experience as the nurses were also trying to avoid drug tolerance in patients. Hence the patients would experience and endure pain when these medications were not administered (due to nurses following standard precautions in medication administration) and sometimes due to drug tolerance from solely relying on medications. Sometimes patients would steal from the medications in the ward and abuse them or have their relatives smuggle in drugs from outside the health facility during visits all in a bid to relieve pain. However these could have been prevented

if non pharmaceutical measures of pain relief were utilized by nurses in these wards (Emuobor, 2024).

Other circumstances I observed include unresponsiveness on the part of the nurses when patients were in pain. This also was due to the fact that they relied solely on medications for pain relief and did not want to overload the drug plasma levels in the patients (Emuobor, 2024).

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Broad objective: the aim of this study is to assess nurses' use of non- pharmaceutical measures of patients' pain relief in a selected tertiary health institution (UBTH) .

Specific objectives: To;

1. determine the various non pharmaceutical measures implemented by nurses in managing patients' pain
2. assess the utilization of non pharmaceutical measures by nurses in the management of patients' pain in selected wards in UBTH
3. identify the factors which influence the choice of various non pharmaceutical methods used in pain management by nurses in selected wards in UBTH.

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the various non pharmaceutical measures that nurses utilize in managing patients pain in UBTH?
2. How often do nurses utilize these non pharmaceutical measures of pain relief in UBTH ?
3. What are the factors that influence the choice of various non pharmaceutical methods used by nurses in UBTH for patients' pain relief?

1.6 HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

There is no relationship between the years of working experience or hierarchical status of nurses and their utilization of non pharmaceutical measures in relieving patients' pain.

1.7 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study is imperative especially for patients who frequently experience pain such as sickle cell patients, cancer patients, pre-operative and post-operative patients as well as women in the labor ward as this would enhance their comfort, reduce their dependency on medications as well as limit occurrence of drug tolerance and abuse . Hence this study holds significance for the following reasons;

1. Improved patient care and outcomes: when implemented effectively, these measures can lead to improved pain relief for patients, leading to better comfort, reduced reliance on medications which also means reduced incidence of drug tolerance and addiction and the overall patient satisfaction
2. Strengthening of the Nursing practice: this study can offer new knowledge that will strengthen the Nursing practice by; identifying areas where nurses require additional training or education with regards to better pain relief practices, identifying barriers and facilitators of this practice and contributing to the growing body of evidence on nonpharmacological pain management thereby adhering to the principle of evidence based practice.
3. The findings from this study can have a broader social impact which will affect the general population positively in the following ways; by reducing healthcare costs through effective pain management which can lead to shorter hospital stay and by improving public health

through promoting best practices in pain management and even increased knowledge and awareness of utilizing these measures by individuals, families, the community at large.

4. For the nurses, it is important because it will elevate their consciousness of the necessity of utilizing non pharmaceutical measures in patients' pain relief as well as improve their overall satisfaction with their practice.

1.8 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study will focus primarily on the nurses from selected wards in the tertiary health facility, University of Benin Teaching Hospital with regards to the following wards: labour ward, medical wards, surgical wards and oncology ward as their utilization of non pharmacological interventions in pain relief will be assessed. This will include Registered nurses, Chief nursing officers and nurses occupying different hierarchies to also determine if there is a relationship between their hierarchy and practice of non pharmacological interventions in pain management.

1.9 OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF TERMS

1. **Non pharmacological measures:** non-pharmacological intervention (NPI) is any type of healthcare intervention which is not primarily based on medication.
2. **Nurses:** According to International Council of Nurses (ICN), a Nurse is a person who has completed a program of basic, generalized nursing education and is authorized by the appropriate regulatory authority to practice nursing in his/her country (ICN, 1987).

3. **Patient's Pain:** The current International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP) defines pain as An unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage (Raja et al, 2020).
4. **Relief:** The feeling associated with the removal of stress or discomfort
5. **Tertiary Health Institution:** This is the third tier of health care, employing specialist services, offered by institutions such as teaching hospitals and units devoted to the care of particular groups—women, children, patients with mental disorders, and so on.
6. **Tertiary Health Care:** highly specialized medical care usually over an extended period of time that involves advanced and complex procedures and treatments performed by medical specialists in state-of-the-art facilities.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this chapter, previous work done related to the non pharmaceutical measures of relieving patients' pain by nurses will be carefully examined under the following headings; Conceptual framework, Empirical framework and Theoretical framework.

2.1 CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

2.1.1 CONCEPT OF PAIN

The International Association for the Study of Pain (IASP, 1979) defines pain as: an unpleasant sensory and/or emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage or described in term of such damage.

The sensation of pain is generated by nerves that send signals to the brain letting it know organs or tissues are damaged or irritated. The brain then sends signals to these organs or muscles to take appropriate action.

Pain can be categorized into various types based on its pathophysiology, duration, and the tissues affected. These include nociceptive pain, neuropathic pain, and psychosomatic pain, each of which involves distinct mechanisms and influences on the individual's overall experience of discomfort.

Types of Pain

1. **Nociceptive Pain:** This is the most common form of pain, resulting from injury to body tissues. It is triggered when nociceptors, specialized pain receptors in the peripheral nervous system, are activated by stimuli such as heat, pressure, or injury (Scholz & Woolf, 2002). Nociceptive

pain can be further classified into somatic and visceral pain, with somatic pain involving skin, muscles, and bones, and visceral pain affecting internal organs.

2. **Neuropathic Pain:** Neuropathic pain arises from damage to the nervous system itself. It is typically characterized by sensations such as burning, tingling, or shooting pain and can occur after conditions such as diabetes, spinal cord injury, or shingles (Baron et al., 2010). Unlike nociceptive pain, which is often responsive to anti-inflammatory medications, neuropathic pain frequently requires treatment with anticonvulsants or antidepressants (Dworkin et al., 2007)
3. **.Psychosomatic Pain:** This type of pain is influenced by emotional and psychological factors. Though there may be no identifiable physical cause, individuals experience real pain sensations. Stress, anxiety, and depression can exacerbate or even initiate pain symptoms in conditions like tension headaches or irritable bowel syndrome (Kroenke et al., 2013).

In medical terms, pain is divided into two categories based on duration :

1. **Acute pain:** which usually comes on suddenly and is caused by something specific. It is sharp in quality. Acute pain usually doesn't last longer than six months. It goes away when there is no longer an underlying cause for the pain. Causes of acute pain include: surgery. Broken bones, dental work, burns or cuts, labor and childbirth (Cleveland Clinic, 2020).

Acute pain typically serves as a protective mechanism, alerting the body to injury or illness and usually resolves once the underlying cause is treated. Chronic pain, however, persists beyond the expected period of healing, often defined as pain lasting more than three to six months (Treede et al., 2015)

2. **Chronic pain** : is pain that is ongoing and usually lasts longer than six months. This type of pain can continue even after the injury or illness that caused it has healed or gone away. Pain signals remain active in the nervous system for weeks, months or years. Some people suffer chronic pain even when there is no past injury or apparent body damage. Chronic pain is linked to conditions that include: headache. Arthritis. cancer, nerve pain. Back pain, fibromyalgia. (Cleveland Clinic, 2020).

Chronic pain, however, persists beyond the expected period of healing, often defined as pain lasting more than three to six months (Treede et al., 2015). Chronic pain can become a disease in its own right, as it leads to significant physical and emotional distress, impacting quality of life and function

Physiological Mechanism of Pain

Pain signals are generated when nociceptors detect harmful stimuli. These signals are then transmitted to the spinal cord via sensory neurons, before being relayed to the brain. In the brain, the thalamus acts as a relay station, sending the pain information to different areas, including the somatosensory cortex (responsible for physical sensation), limbic system (emotional response), and prefrontal cortex (cognitive interpretation) (Basbaum et al., 2009). Neurotransmitters such as substance P, glutamate, and prostaglandins play a role in modulating pain transmission, while the body's endogenous opioid system, including endorphins, acts to mitigate pain (Millan, 2002). This complex interplay of pathways means that pain perception is not just a simple sensory event, but is also influenced by emotional, cognitive, and contextual factors.

The Subjective Nature of Pain

The subjective nature of pain makes it difficult to measure objectively. Pain perception varies between individuals, influenced by factors such as genetics, cultural background, previous experiences, and emotional state (Gatchel et al., 2007). The McGill Pain Questionnaire and Visual Analog Scale (VAS) are commonly used tools to help quantify pain, although these rely heavily on self-reporting .

Pain Management Approaches:

Pain management must be holistic, considering not only the physical but also the emotional and psychological dimensions of the experience. Treatment options include pharmacological interventions such as NSAIDs, opioids, and neuropathic pain medications, alongside non-pharmacological methods such as physical therapy, cognitive-behavioral therapy, and alternative therapies like acupuncture (Finnerup et al., 2015).

Pain Modulation: Pain modulation is the process of alterations in the pain signals along the transmission pathway of pain. It explains:

1. Why individuals respond to the same stimulus differently.
2. The mechanism of action when using clinical analgesia (Pain-Modulation Physiopedia.com) .

Endorphins, the body's natural painkillers, can reduce pain perception. Additionally, pain perception is affected by emotions, previous pain experiences, expectancies related to pain (or pain relief), contextual factors, and attentional processes (Pain Perception- an Overview, Science Direct Topics)

Pain Threshold and Tolerance: Pain is measured in one of the two ways, either using pain threshold or using pain tolerance. Pain threshold is simply the measurement of when the research participant begins to be aware of his or her pain, whereas pain tolerance is when the participant can no longer tolerate the painful stimulus and either withdraws or asks the researcher to stop the stimulus (Pain Threshold- an Overview, Science Direct Topics)

Pain threshold as it relates to sensitivity to pressure is measured with an algometer. Pain tolerance, on the other hand, is the greatest level of pain that a subject is prepared to endure. Tolerance varies much more widely across subjects and depends on prescribed medications.(Pain Threshold- an Overview, Science Direct Topics).

Pain tolerance is the maximum level of pain that a person is able to tolerate. Pain tolerance is distinct from pain threshold (the point at which pain begins to be felt) (Pain tolerance Wikipedia)

The American Pain Society (APS) introduced the “pain as the 5th vital sign” concept in 1996 to lessen the burden of under assessing and treating pain (Araujo & Romero, 2015; Levy et al., 2018; Liyew et al., 2020).

A study in the United Kingdom revealed that hospital-wide pain prevalence obtained ranged from 37.7–84%, severe pain prevalence ranged from 9–36%. The papers reviewed were of variable quality and heterogeneous resulting in the wide range of pain prevalence.

Higher prevalence of pain was found for surgical patients compared to medical patients, although up to 55% of medical patients’ reported pain (Gregory et al. 2016) .

2.1.2 TYPES OF NON PHARMACOLOGICAL PAIN MANAGEMENT INTERVENTIONS

Non-pharmacological methods do not replace pharmacological treatments but are complementary to medication treatments. These strategies are worthwhile especially for managing mild to moderate pain (Mohamed Bayoumi et al., 2021). They are used along with medication for moderate to high-intensity pain control and alone for treatment of low-intensity pain.

Non-pharmacological pain management interventions are divided into three main categories ; The first one is physical interventions, like massage, positioning, heat and cold therapy, transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), acupuncture, and progressive muscle relaxation. The second one is psychological therapy. The third type is other therapies, including spirituality and religious activities as well as music therapy and listening to Qur'an (El Geziry A et al, 2018; Abdollahyar A et al, 2019).

According to a study conducted on nurses' use of non pharmacological pain management methods in the ICU in Iran, the most common non-pharmacological pain management methods include music therapy, relaxation techniques, repositioning, the use of a cold compress, respiratory and deep breathing exercises, massage, diet, prayer, exercise, the use of calming voices, and the provision of information.

Other non-pharmacological interventions, such as using guided imagery, video and audio tapes, and therapeutic communication, do not require much of the nurses' time. These interventions may also be effective in improving the symptoms of patients undergoing mechanical ventilation in ICUs (Zeinab et al, 2021).

Another study done in a tertiary health institution in Egypt El-Mansura University Hospital, Egypt revealed that some common non pharmacological measures that a nurse can utilize without a

doctor's order are: Physical therapies such as thermal regulation, massaging and positioning ; Cognitive behavioral methods such as imagery, distraction techniques, relaxation techniques, breathing techniques, and positive reinforcement; Others like emotional support, positive family involvement and comfortable environment (Khonji et al, 2021).

They include a broad range of Interventions which can be used to relieve pain without the use of medications. There are generally categorized into three groups; Physical therapies, Psychological therapies and Complementary therapies.

1. Physical therapies : Physical therapies focus on using physical modalities to directly address the source of pain or promote relaxation and enhance relief of pain (McNett et al, 2020).

Heat and cold therapy: this involves the application of heat (hot compress) or cold packs to the afflicted area which helps reduce inflammation and pain (McNett et al, 2020).

Massage therapy which improves blood circulation reduce muscle tension and promote relaxation, leading to pain relief .

Acupuncture: this is a traditional Chinese technique which involves inserting of thin needles into specific points on the body. Acupuncture has been shown to be effective for pain relief in some conditions (Acupuncture Review Board, 2018)

According to a research done in Pakistan on Evaluating the efficiency of non pharmacological pain management during labor and delivery; these techniques include relaxation exercises, acupuncture, breathing techniques, hydrotherapy, massage, visualization, positioning, and aromatherapy (Czech et al., 2018).

Each technique targets distinct aspects of pain perception and coping mechanisms to reduce pain intensity, enhance relaxation, and foster a sense of control and empowerment

during labor (Jones et al., 2012; Smith et al., 2018). Multiple studies have examined the efficacy of non-pharmaceutical pain management techniques in enhancing childbirth experiences. According to research, these techniques can reduce pain intensity, reduce the need for pharmacological interventions, and improve maternal satisfaction (Zuarez-Easton et al., 2023). By activating the body's natural pain-relieving mechanisms, relaxation techniques such as deep breathing, guided imagery, and progressive muscle relaxation have alleviated pain and promoted relaxation (Jones et al., 2012; Thomson et al., 2019). Massage and hydrotherapy have also demonstrated promise in reducing labor discomfort. Massage techniques, such as effleurage and counter-pressure, can promote the release of endorphins, the body's natural painkillers, while providing physical solace and relaxation (Daries, 2023).

Hydrotherapy, which involves massaging, has been shown to alleviate pain, promote relaxation, and expedite labor (Mooventhana and Nivethitha, 2014).

Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) involves applying low-level electrical currents to the skin using electrodes placed near the painful area. TENS operates on the principle of the gate control theory of pain modulation. According to this theory, the nervous system can only process a limited amount of sensory input at a time. By stimulating non-painful sensory nerves through TENS, the incoming "gate" for pain signals can be partially closed, reducing the transmission of pain signals to the brain. There are other mechanisms for its action and include CNS modulation, segmental inhibitions etc. (Rajeev Gupta, 2023).

Physical therapy or physiotherapy is a common non-pharmaceutical approach to pain management, and involves a range of exercises and techniques designed to improve

strength, flexibility, and range of motion. Studies have shown that physical therapy can be effective in reducing pain and improving function in patients with chronic pain conditions such as low back pain and osteoarthritis (3). This offers benefits such as pain reduction, enhanced mobility, and improved quality of life and the mechanisms of benefit is due to endorphin release, anti-inflammatory effects, and central nervous system modulation.

(Rajeev Gupta, 2023).

2. Psychological therapies: According to a study done in Northwestern Ethiopia on “Non Pharmacological Pain Management Practice and Associated Factors Among Nurses Working at Comprehensive Specialized Hospital “ findings indicate that; Cognitive behavioral and psychological therapies which include relaxations, patient education, breathing techniques, and attention distraction are important NPPM practices. Other NPPM practices include emotional support/reassurance, touching, and creating a comfortable environment (He et al., 2011;Kidanemariam et al., 2020). Meditation practices foster mindfulness, emotional regulation, and pain perception alteration (Gupta, 2023). Cognitive-behavioural therapy (CBT) is a form of talk therapy that focuses on identifying and changing negative thought patterns and behaviours that may be contributing to the experience of pain. CBT may be useful for patients with chronic pain conditions such as fibromyalgia and chronic headache, and has been shown to improve pain, mood, and quality of life in some patients). CBT operates through cognitive restructuring, behavioral modification, and pain perception modulation (Gupta, 2023).
3. Complementary therapies encompass a diverse range of approaches that are not considered part of traditional Western medicine. They include Aromatherapy: use of essential oils which may provide some pain relief, although the evidence is mixed (Huntley et al,2008);

Yoga which can improve flexibility, strength and relaxation which all contribute to pain management (Cramer et al, 2013). Others may include Tai Chi amongst others.

2.1.3. BENEFITS OF NON PHARMACOLOGICAL PAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

Benefits of the non pharmacological interventions for pain relief include:

1. They are generally safer and have fewer side effects than many pain medications, and may also be more cost-effective in the long-term.
2. Additionally, non-pharmaceutical approaches may be particularly useful for patients who have not responded well to traditional pharmacological interventions, or who may be at risk for adverse effects from pain medications.
3. Non pharmacological therapies are certainly less expensive and more applicable, as many alternative strategies, such as cognitive-behavioral therapy, physical therapy, emotional therapy, and patient family involvement, can be used (Magda Mohamed Mohamed Bayoumi et al, 2021).
4. According to the study done by Mohamed Bayoumi MM, Khonji LMA, Gabr WFM (2021), the following are identified benefits to the use of non pharmacological measures of pain management; less side effects, less expensive, less dependency, more available than medications, it is relaxing and patients can practice and use them post- discharge.

2.1.4 LIMITATIONS OF NON PHARMACOLOGICAL PAIN MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

It is also important to note that non-pharmaceutical approaches to pain management may not be suitable for all patients. Patients with certain medical conditions or who are taking certain

medications may not be able to use certain non-pharmaceutical interventions. For example, patients taking blood thinners may not be able to use acupuncture, as the insertion of needles can increase the risk of bleeding. In addition, non-pharmaceutical approaches to pain management may take longer to produce results than pharmacological interventions. Patients may need to be patient and committed to their treatment plan in order to see significant improvements in their pain symptoms (Gupta, 2023).

2.1.5 NURSES' RESPONSIBILITIES AND SKILLS REQUIRED IN NON PHARMACOLOGICAL MANAGEMENT OF PAIN

Implementation of effective non-pharmacological management requires knowledgeable, skillful nurses. Many studies have shown that nurses require more knowledge about non-pharmacological management to reduce patients' pain intensity (Bayoumi M. M, Khonji L. M. A, Gabr W. F. M, 2021).

According to a research done by Gupta, 2023, healthcare providers should : Work with patients to develop personalized treatment plans that take into account the patient's medical history, lifestyle factors, and individual preferences. Additionally, it is important for healthcare providers to be knowledgeable about the various non-pharmaceutical approaches to pain management and to be able to offer these interventions to patients when appropriate. This may involve additional training or education for healthcare providers to ensure that they are equipped to provide effective non-pharmaceutical pain management strategies. Finally, research into the effectiveness of non-pharmaceutical approaches to pain management is ongoing, and new interventions and techniques are being developed all the time. It is important for healthcare providers to stay up-to-date with the latest research and to continually evaluate the effectiveness of non-pharmaceutical pain

management strategies in their patients . Non-pharmaceutical approaches to chronic pain management are an important area of research and clinical practice. By offering a range of interventions that take into account the individual patient’s needs and preferences, healthcare providers can help improve pain management outcomes for all patients.

By taking a biopsychosocial approach to pain management and addressing all aspects of the pain experience, healthcare providers can develop more effective treatment plans that improve outcomes and reduce the risk of long-term disability and dependence on pharmacological interventions (Gupta, 2023).

2.1.6 BARRIERS TO THE USE OF NON PHARMACOLOGICAL MEASURES OF PAIN MANAGEMENT

1. According to the study done by Bayoumi M. M, Khonji L. M. A, Gabr W. F. M, 2021, the following were identified barriers to the use of non pharmacological measures of pain management by nurses, these are;

patients’ unwillingness, lack of time, lack of knowledge, being hard to measure, pain too severe, age of the patient, patients’ health beliefs, lack of equipment.

2. In another study carried out by Gupta, 2023 , the following were identified barriers to the implementation of non pharmacological interventions in pain management:

A. Firstly the lack of awareness among healthcare providers and patients regarding the availability and effectiveness of these interventions. Educating healthcare providers and patients about the benefits and limitations of non-pharmaceutical approaches to pain management can help increase their use and improve pain management outcome.

B. Secondly is the lack of insurance coverage for non-pharmaceutical interventions. In many countries, insurance companies do not cover the cost of non-pharmaceutical interventions, which can limit their accessibility for patients who cannot afford to pay out of pocket.

C. Thirdly research into non-pharmaceutical approaches to pain management is still in its early stages, and more rigorous studies are needed to establish their safety and efficacy.

3. According to a qualitative study carried out by Israa A. M. Abuijlan, Priyalatha Muthu, and Manju Nair Avinash (2023), nurses identified some of their encountered barriers in implementing non pharmacological pain management measures in their practice in two forms;

A. barriers due to patient factors

B. and barriers due to nurses' factors.

A. Barrier due to patient factors were the patient's pain sensitivity (tolerance) level, short-duration effect, and patient's poor knowledge. One of the nurses mentioned that most of the patients are very sensitive to pain; therefore, analgesics are the first choice for instant relief. Furthermore, nurses mentioned that the shorter effect of NPPCM lowers its preference for fast-acting analgesics. According to a nurse respondent, NPPC measures are effective only for one hour then pain will increase and they would ask for painkillers and some patients think fast pain relief will stop the elevation of pain intensity that's why they ask for analgesics first.

In addition, nurses described that patients' lack of knowledge regarding the advantages of NPPCM negatively affects the utilization of NPPCMs. According to some of the nurse respondents the majority of patients do not know the benefits of NPPCM and this leads to poor cooperation which

takes us time to convince them about the benefits of these measures. Some patients do not know the side effects of analgesics and hence do not understand their negative effects on their health.

B. Barriers due to nurses' factors were workload, limited resources, and inadequate healthcare professional support. In the words of a respondent, a common challenge they faced was time, such as when there was more admission and procedures or when staff were on sick leave. During busy working days, there was no time to explain to the patient the benefits of NPPCM, especially with uncooperative patients so they gave them prescribed medication.

Another factor on the part of the nurses was limited resources, such as the activity room which would have contributed to effective use of NPPCM. A respondent stated that though there is free access to WIFI in the hospital yet having an activity room or some space is good for diversional activities. Sometimes it is difficult to keep a patient in a single room. So, creating a quiet environment when two patients share same room is impossible.

According to this study, on the issue of inadequate health care profession support, nurses faced difficulties utilizing the NPPCM when physicians were poorly involved in convincing patients to accept NPPCM, also the absence of physiotherapists can interfere with patients' pain control. In addition, nurses mentioned that the inactivation of the pain management nurse role interferes with the nurse's utilization of NPPCM. In the words of some of the respondents, some physicians are not making enough effort to convince the patient to try NPPCM, also taking care of a patient with musculoskeletal disorders is a complete team responsibility. For example, a physiotherapist can assist the patient with some exercise to strengthen the muscle and reduce pain. The nurses also admitted lacking the role of pain management nurse who is qualified and well-trained to utilize NPPCM. She can contribute effectively to nurses' practice by better implementation of NPPCM.

2.2 THEORETICAL REVIEW

This will be based on Comfort Theory by Katharine Kolcaba .

Figure 2.1 : Conceptual Framework for Comfort Theory

Pain management is a critical aspect of patient care in healthcare settings, and nurses play a pivotal role in this process. While pharmaceutical interventions are commonly used, non-pharmaceutical measures (NPMs) have gained recognition for their effectiveness in pain relief. Comfort Theory, developed by Katharine Kolcaba, provides a comprehensive framework to understand and enhance patient comfort, including the use of NPMs in pain management.

2.2.1 Comfort Theory Overview

Comfort Theory, proposed by Kolcaba in the 1990s, is a middle-range nursing theory that emphasizes the importance of comfort in patient care. According to Kolcaba, comfort is a holistic experience encompassing physical, psychospiritual, environmental, and sociocultural dimensions.

The theory posits that comfort is a desirable outcome of nursing care and that interventions should be designed to enhance comfort across these dimensions (Kolcaba, 2003).

Kolcaba described comfort as existing in 3 forms: relief, ease, and transcendence. Also, Kolcaba described 4 contexts in which patient comfort can occur: physical, psychospiritual, environmental, and sociocultural.

Relief is defined as the experience of having had a specified need met (Kolcaba, 1991). Ease is defined as a state of calm or contentment (Kolcaba, 1991). Transcendence is defined as a state in which ordinary powers are enhanced (Paterson and Zderad, 1976). According to Kolcaba, the characteristic that distinguishes transcendence from the other two states is that transcendence designates the patients' potential for extraordinary performance as an end. Comfort is a desirable outcome for nursing care because it facilitates gains in physical and/ or psychological performance (Kolcaba , 1994).

The first context is the physical which pertains to bodily sensations. The second context is the psycho-spiritual pertaining to the internal awareness of self, including esteem, sexuality, meaning in one's life, and relationship to a higher order or being. The third context is social, pertaining to interpersonal, family and cultural relationships. Also included under social comforts are the financial and informational aspects of social life. The fourth context in which comfort is

experienced is the environmental, pertaining to light, noise ambience, colours, temperature and natural versus synthetic elements (Kolcaba, 1991).

The four contexts were juxtaposed with the three types of comfort, creating a taxonomic structure (matrix) from which to consider the complexities of comfort as an outcome (figure 2.2) .

		Type of Comfort		
		Relief	Ease	Transcendence
Context in Which Comfort Occurs	Physical			
	Psychospiritual			
	Environmental			
	Social			

Type of Comfort:

Relief: The state of a patient who has had a specific need met

Ease: The state of calm or contentment

Transcendence: The state in which one rises above one's problems or pain

Context in Which Comfort Occurs:

Physical: Pertaining to bodily sensations

Psychospiritual: Pertaining to internal awareness of self, including esteem, concept, sexuality, and meaning in one's life; one's relationship to a higher order or being

Environmental: Pertaining to the external surroundings, conditions, and influences

Social: Pertaining to interpersonal, family, and societal relationships

Figure 2.2 : Kolcaba Theory

Holistic comfort is defined as the immediate experience of being strengthened through having the needs for relief, ease, and transcendence met in four contexts of experience (physical, psychospiritual, social, and environmental) (Kolcaba, 2010).

Some major concepts and definitions outlined in the Comfort Theory include:

1. **Health care needs** are comfort needs arising from stressful health care situations that cannot be met by recipients' traditional support systems. The needs may be physical, psychospiritual, sociocultural, or environmental. They become apparent through monitoring, verbal or nonverbal reports, pathophysiological parameters, education and support, and financial counseling and intervention (Kolcaba, 2003).
2. **Comfort interventions** are nursing actions and referrals designed to address specific comfort needs of recipients, including physiological, social, cultural, financial, psychological, spiritual, environmental, and physical interventions (Kolcaba, 2001).
3. **Intervening variables** are interacting forces that influence recipients' perceptions of total comfort. They consist of past experiences, age, attitude, emotional state, support system, prognosis, finances, education, cultural background, and the totality of elements in the recipients' experience (Kolcaba, 1994). Such intervening variables have an impact on planning and success of patient care interventions.
4. **Comfort** is the state experienced by recipients of comfort interventions. It is the immediate, holistic experience of being strengthened when one's needs are addressed for three types of comfort (relief, ease, and transcendence) in four contexts (physical, psychospiritual, sociocultural, and environmental) (Kolcaba, 1994)

5. **Institutional integrity:** Corporations, communities, schools, hospitals, regions, states, and countries that possess the qualities of being complete, whole, sound, upright, appealing, ethical, and sincere possess institutional integrity. When an institution displays this type of integrity, it produces evidence for best practices and best policies (Kolcaba, 2001).
6. **Health-seeking behaviors** compose a broad category of outcomes related to the pursuit of health as defined by the recipient(s) in consultation with the nurse. The category was synthesized by Schlotfeldt (1975) and proposed to be internal, external, or a peaceful death.
7. **Best practice :** The use of health care interventions based on evidence to produce the best possible patient and family (institutional) outcomes is known as best practices
8. **Best policies:** Institutional or regional policies ranging from protocols for procedures and medical conditions to access and delivery of health care are known as best policies (Thérèse Dowd, 2017).

2.2.2 Application Of Comfort Theory To The Study

Comfort theory, developed by Katharine Kolcaba, can be applied to the study in several ways which include:

1. **Holistic Comfort:** Comfort theory emphasizes holistic care, addressing physical, psychospiritual, environmental, and sociocultural comfort. Non-pharmacological pain management strategies align well with this approach as they often incorporate methods that provide relief beyond just the physical symptoms of pain. Techniques such as relaxation exercises, cognitive-behavioral strategies, and complementary therapies (e.g., massage, acupuncture) can enhance overall patient comfort.

2. **Patient-Centered Care:** Comfort theory supports the idea of individualized care plans based on the specific comfort needs of each patient. Nurses can assess and implement nonpharmacological measures tailored to the patient's preferences and conditions. This might include music therapy for a patient who finds it relaxing or guided imagery for someone who responds well to visualization techniques.
3. **Assessment of Comfort:** According to Kolcaba, comfort is a desirable outcome of healthcare. Nurses can use comfort theory to systematically assess a patient's comfort levels and determine the effectiveness of non-pharmacological interventions. Tools and scales developed from comfort theory can help quantify improvements in comfort and guide further care decisions.
4. **Enhanced Healing Environment:** Comfort theory underscores the importance of a healing environment. Non-pharmacological measures often include modifications to the patient's environment, such as reducing noise, adjusting lighting, or creating a more soothing atmosphere. These environmental changes can significantly impact the patient's comfort and perception of pain.
5. **Empowerment and Autonomy:** Comfort theory aligns with empowering patients and respecting their autonomy. Non-pharmacological pain management often involves teaching patients self-care techniques, such as deep breathing exercises or mindfulness practices. This empowers patients to take an active role in managing their pain and enhances their sense of control and comfort.
6. **Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Implementing non-pharmacological measures often requires collaboration among various healthcare professionals, including physical therapists, psychologists, and complementary therapy practitioners. Comfort theory

supports a collaborative approach to care, emphasizing that a multidisciplinary team can best address the diverse comfort needs of patients.

By integrating comfort theory into the practice of using non-pharmacological measures for pain management, nurses can provide more comprehensive, patient-centered, and effective care. This approach not only helps in managing pain but also enhances the overall well-being and comfort of patients in tertiary health institutions.

2.3 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

2.3.1 The Various Non-pharmacological Measures Of Pain Management

According to a study carried out by Umar et al (2023), in Kano State Nigeria, the study aimed to assess the knowledge and practice of non-pharmacological pain management techniques among nurses and midwives in Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital (AKTH), Kano State, Nigeria. A total of one hundred and four (104) questionnaires were distributed to the respondents in the study. Eighty five (85) questionnaires representing 82% were returned completed and so analysis was based on 85 respondents. The results showed that 58.8% of the respondents had poor knowledge of nonpharmacological pain management techniques, only 3.5% of them had very good knowledge. The study also revealed that most of the respondents 95.3% have practiced at least one of the techniques, it was revealed that changing position was the most practiced technique by 71.8% of the respondents. Other methods practiced included according to the results of the study revealed that overwhelming majority (95.3%) had at least practiced one of the non-pharmacological pain management techniques at one time or the other, 71.8%, have ever practiced position changes, 63.5% massage, 47.1% distraction, 65.9% heat/cold, 70.6% reassurance and 49.4% patient's

family involvement to relieve patient's pain respectively, however, only 25.9% and 7.1% make use of imagery and biofeedback.

According to a study carried out by Israa A. M. Abuijlan, Priyalatha Muthu, and Manju Nair Avinash (2023), the aim of the study was to explore the nurses' experience and perceived challenges in using non pharmacological pain measures in caring for patients with musculoskeletal pain. The study was conducted in the medical and orthopedic ward of an accredited government hospital in Ras-Al Khaimah, United Arab Emirates. Eleven nurses who consented to participate were selected using a purposive sampling technique. The target population group was registered nurses with more than 1 year of experience in the orthopedics and medical inpatient units. A total of eleven nurses were interviewed (two males and nine females). Two nurses were interviewed individually daily, and written verbatim and audio recordings were obtained. The interviews were conducted in English language. Each interview lasted between 25 and 35 minutes. The average age of nurses is 29 years (SD =6.3). The average years of nursing experience is 8.45 (SD =8.27) while the years of caring for patients with Musculoskeletal pain is 8.27 (SD =3.3). All of the participants have a Bachelor of Science in Nursing degree.

The types of non pharmacological pain management used by the nurses included stabilizing the affected limb and applying ice therapy to the fractured part reduced the patient's pain, encouraging the patients to do breathing exercises which aided their comfort, taking patients to the hospital's ground floor (garden) during the sunset which reduced their complaints, application of heat compress for lower back pain, stabilizing fractured limbs and applying ice therapy, massaging patients with muscular spasms and scheduling arthritic patients for physiotherapy.

According to a study carried out by Aster Shiferaw et al (2020) on utilization of labor pain management methods and associated factors among obstetric care givers at public health institutions of East Gojjam Zone, Amhara region, Ethiopia, facility based cross-sectional study : the aim of this study was to assess utilization of labor pain management methods and associated factors among obstetric care givers in the study setting.. Three hundred and five participants were responded to questioners with a response rate of 94.4% .The mean age of the respondents was 28.3 years (SD \pm 4.1). The majority of the respondents, 213 (69.8%), were among the age group of 20–29 .Among the respondents, 195 (63.9%) were male and 287(94.1%) were orthodox religious followers. The majority of the respondents, 150 (49.2%), were midwives, 182 (59.7%) were BSc holders and 175 (57.4%) of respondents had less than 5 years' experience. Among the total respondents, about 298(97.7%) knew about labor pain management methods. From them, 215 (70.5%) knew both pharmacological and non-pharmacological methods, 74(24.8%) only nonpharmacological and 9(3%) knew only pharmacological methods.

The results of this study revealed that among the non-pharmacological methods, the most well-known one is psychotherapy response by 219 (71.8%) respondents. Next 159 (52.1%), 155(50.8%), 150 (49.2%) and 127(41.6%) responds allow the mother to ambulate, massage the back ,relaxation & breathing technique and show the patient how to bear down respectively. The remaining were music therapy 62 (20. 3%), diversional therapy 22(7.2%), Transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation 16(5.2%) and acupuncture 11 (3.6%).

According to a study carried out by Shegaw Zeleke, Amare Kassaw, and Yeshambaw Eshetie (2021), on : Non-Pharmacological Pain Management Practice And Barriers Among Nurses Working in Debre Tabor Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Ethiopia; the study aimed to assess non-pharmacological pain management practice and barriers among nurses working in Debre

Tabor Comprehensive Specialized Hospital, Ethiopia. The study was conducted from October 1st to December 30, 2020 with descriptive cross-sectional study design. The study populations were all nurses (N = 169) working in Debre Tabor Comprehensive Specialized Hospital wards (Medical ward, Surgical ward, Intensive Care Unit ward, Orthopedic Ward, Pediatrics ward, Psychiatry ward, Emergency ward, Recovery ward). About three fourth 125 (74%) of nurses marital status were married. Regarding educational status 132 (78.1%) were qualified with BSc degree in nursing, and only 24(14.2%) of nurses had training on non -pharmacology pain management as seen in Table1.

Regarding to nurses non pharmacology pain management practice, 37(21.9%) of nurses apply movement restriction/resting, 31(18.3%) routinely use therapeutic communication with patient and family, 26(15.4%) apply hot or cold local packages routinely and 9(5.3%) of nurses provide quiet and comfortable room/reduce light intensity and alarms for the patients as nonpharmacological pain management. But, 169(100%) of nurses were never used acupuncture/acupressure as non-pharmacology patient pain management method. The overall non- pharmacology pain management practice level of nurses in Debre Tabor Comprehensive Specialized Hospital showed that only 44(26%) of nurses had good practice on non- pharmacology pain management methods, this is seen in Table 2 of the study.

According to a study carried out by Jabir Abdella, Zewdie Oltaye and Diriba Fetene (2021), on Knowledge and Practice of Nurses towards Non-Pharmacological Pain Management Methods and Associated Factors at West Arsi Zone Public Hospitals, Oromia, Ethiopia, 2021: A Cross-Sectional Institution Based Study in which 418 nurses were included in the study with a response rate of 99%. Among the participants, 245(58.6%) were males and the age of participants was in the range

of 20 to 50 with the mean age of 29.04(\pm SD=4.6) years. Of the participants, 230 (55%) were married and 325(77.8%) were BSc holders. Among them, 162(38.8%) nurses had 3-5 years of experience with a mean of 5.12 years of work experience and with a minimum and maximum of 1 and 30 years, respectively. Among the participants, 297 (71.1) had reported having monthly income above 4000 Ethiopian Birr (Table: 1).

Three hundred thirty-one (79.2%) respondents were reported that providing a suitable room temperature and good air condition can alleviate pain. Also, 332(79.4%) reported that providing the patient with a possibility to rest by minimizing noise can alleviate pain. Three hundred twenty-five (77.8%) of study participants were correctly answered as pain can be alleviated by position changes. Among participants,309(73.9%) were aware of the benefits of non-pharmacological pain management, but about 132(31.6%) study participants were answered incorrectly as nonpharmacological pain management only includes distraction, heat or cold, and relaxation, and also 23.9% of nurses responded that Non-drug interventions are effective only for mild pain control (Table:5).

Among the respondents, 142 (34.0%) answer as sometimes orders the patient to Breath when she or he feels pain. Of the respondents, only 11(2.6%) reported always use breathing and distraction methods to alleviate patient's pain, and also 147(35.2%) reported as sometimes they use positioning to relieve pain. Massaging 142 (34.0%), staying with the patient when he or she feels pain167 (40.0%), and comforting and reassurance were mostly reported to be practiced as "sometimes" (Table 7). Data of this study was collected through a questionnaire, so the results of this study might have been affected by subjects' response bias and, also the cross-sectional nature of the study limits the cause-effect relationship.

According to a study carried out by Timothy Aghogho EHWARIEME, Uzezi JOSIAH and Oluwaseun Oluwafunmilayo ABIODUN on : Postoperative Pain Assessment and Management Among Nurses in selected hospitals in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria; the study was designed to determine the nurse assessment of postoperative pain and its management in selected hospitals, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. Target population were nurses from nursing officer II to Chief nursing officer cadres who work in the various surgical Wards/units only of the selected health facilities. They were 222. A purposive sampling technique was employed to recruit participants for the study. All the target population who meet the inclusion criteria were used for the study as the target population is small. The inclusion criteria were as follows: those registered with the Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria; an employee of the selected health facilities ; those who have worked in the surgical wards/units of the selected health facility for not <6 months. The results of the study showed that ; providing clean, calm, and well-ventilated ward environment with a mean score of 3.69 ± 0.61 was the most used nonpharmacological method, followed by distraction, relaxation, and guided imagery with a mean score of 3.52 ± 0.50 , dressing, bandage, splint, and reinforce wound sites postoperatively with a mean score of 3.39 ± 0.54 , and early ambulation/exercise” with a mean score of 3.20 ± 0.62 [Figure 2]. The results as indicated in figure 2 of the study shows some of the non pharmacological interventions utilized by the nurses in managing post operative pain, these are : provision of clean, calm, and a well-ventilated ward environment, use of patient distraction, relaxation and guided imagery postoperatively to reduce pain, use of massaging and stretching to reduce post-operative pain, application of heat and cold compresses, encouraging the use of acupuncture, encouraging early ambulation/exercise, dress, bandage, splint, and reinforcing wound sites.

According to a study carried out by G. K. Eke and L. E. Yaguo Ide (2020) on Non-pharmacological

Management of Procedural Pain in Children: Health Worker's Approach at a Tertiary Health Facility, Southern Nigeria, the study was conducted with the aim to determine health workers' approach towards non-pharmacological management of procedural pain in children at the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH). This was descriptive cross-sectional study was carried out between November 2019 and January 2020. The study population consisted of doctors and nurses who care for children at the department of pediatrics of the UPTH. Their years of work experience ranged from between <5years to >15 years and they all consented for the study. Data was collected using a semi-structured and self-administered questionnaire consisting of 3 sections was used to collect information. Distraction was the most common strategy mentioned as non-pharmacological measure by respondents (n=85, 84.2%), followed by positioning (n=58, 57.4%) while 15(14.9%) knew about hypnosis. Overall the results of this study pointed out the following as nonpharmacological interventions utilized by the nurses and doctors as listed out in Table 4: Distractions ; Positioning/Restrictions; Cuddling/ Soothing; Breathing Exercises; Warm /Cold compress; Breast feeding; Resilience ; Encouragement; Massage; Relaxation ; Acupuncture; Hypnosis; Psychotherapy ; Counselling ; Hydrotherapy ; Health education; Life style change; Placebo ; And Those Not indicated. This study had a very clear, rich and precise presentation of outcomes, however the main focus was on the pediatrics department, which limited the scope of utilization of nonpharmacological interventions for patients' pain relief as it would have encompassed a wider variety of non pharmacological interventions if the study included other nurses from other wards like ICU, labour ward, orthopedic, medical wards, surgical wards, oncology and so on.

2.3.2 Nurses' Utilization Of Non pharmacological Management Of Patients' Pain

In a study carried out by Limakatso Elizabeth Parkies, Daphne Murray and Uchenna Benedine Okafor (2024), on The Benefits and Barriers of Providing Non-Pharmacological Pain Relief to Women in Labour during COVID-19: A Qualitative Study of Midwives in South Africa; the participants were all black female midwives (n = 10) with extensive professional experience in midwifery (ranging from 3–27 years) and between the ages of 28 and 55 years. The participants had diplomas in Nursing (General, Psychiatry, and Community) and Midwifery. They were responsible for providing safe, maternal healthcare to women in the wards and/or antenatal care. The participants were interviewed at two district hospitals in Matjhabeng Municipality, Lejweleputswa District, Free State Province of South Africa. The results of this study was highlighted using three themes;

1. Experiences using non-pharmacological methods;
 2. Challenges of non-pharmacological pain relief and
 3. Suggestions for improvements in non-pharmacological pain relief utilization.
1. Based on the experiences of nurse midwives who participated in the study, they reported utilizing non-pharmacological approaches to help women ease birth pain, believing them to be beneficial. These include mobilization exercises, warm baths/showers, breathing exercises, and back rubs. The above-cited techniques serve to distract attention from the source of the pain and have a calming effect. The following are statements from participants in the study : Non-pharmacological pain relief is still working like mobilizing the patient, sending the patients to the shower, as well as deep breathing. Every patient is different. We usually use the rubbing method. We let them walk, take a shower, and then do breathing exercises. We also encourage

them to take a warm bath because it does help with pain management. Also some of these nurse midwives emphasized the importance of the presence of companions assisting in back massaging and thereby facilitating continuity of care as seen in the following statements; We used to allow patients to bring in their companions, who were helpful in rubbing the patient's back and helping with continuity of care. They can even call you if the woman requires your assistance. During the times before COVID we used to allow companions and we would ask them to rub the woman. The rubbing method were working well because the husband or the mother will be there. Even with these positive experiences of the participants, some of the participants also verbalized that non-pharmacological treatments are sometimes ineffective in decreasing labour pain as compared to pharmacological therapies, as women occasionally continue to experience labour pain. This is seen in the following statements; We do not encourage the use of pharmacological interventions, but non-pharmacological interventions are more effective when combined with pharmacological interventions for certain women . This method is like drug treatments, but each patient is different; it works for some but doesn't for others . A few participants also mentioned that non-pharmacological approaches, such as warm showers, might often exacerbate pain rather than ease it. Midwives allowed birth companions to be present to provide emotional support to the women; Then, after taking a warm shower, I noticed that the woman's pains got worse instead of better. Some say the pain is worse after taking a bath .

2. Based on challenges encountered in the use of non-pharmacological pain relief by the nurse midwives, the Insufficient availability of staff contributes to suboptimal pain treatment, leading to the poor provision of necessary care for women. This can result in women becoming intolerant and experiencing increased discomfort with each contraction, which

can lead to complications such as fetal distress. Most participants expressed awareness regarding their responsibilities; yet, due to a scarcity of personnel, they encountered difficulties in successfully addressing labour pain. As a result, many people avoid receiving back massages; We don't do massaging because of shortage of staff ; We are also unable to rub/massage the woman because of lack of time and shortage of Staff . According to some participants, due to cultural beliefs, some African women choose not to have birth partners ; The challenge is that not all of them who are coming with a companion. Our Black patients are not coming with their companions, only few are coming with a companion. We do allow companions, but it is extremely rare, the patients always come alone. I would say that only a few out of every five people come with a friend or family member. Most participants reported that some women were hesitant, uncooperative, and unwilling to move or perform breathing exercises. Some women do not take advantage of available facilities, which include warm bathing or mobilizing, because they view these activities as punishment instead of a benefit. Sometimes, patients are hesitant to move because they don't understand why the sister says I have to walk when I'm in pain. They are irritable and do not comprehend why they should take a warm bath, even when we explain why they should ; The patients sometimes do not cooperate in terms of mobilizing breathing exercises because they don't understand why they should do it ; You will tell them Madam go take a bath, sit in there for as long as you can or for about 30 min then you go and attend to another patient, not even five minutes, then the patient is out from Bath . Women are frequently unable to take a warm bath or shower due to shortages of warm water in maternity wards; Sometimes there will be no warm water; they will come back saying sister you said I should take a shower, but it's only cold water). Some participants noted that the

lack of space in labour wards prevented them from encouraging physical activity among women; We are unable to conduct the exercises due to a lack of space and also staffing owing to the fact that you must be present

3. Finally based on the suggestions on improving the utilization of non pharmacological interventions for patients' pain relief the midwives suggested educating women; increasing the number of midwives, doulas or students; providing the necessary facilities; and combining the two pain management approaches (pharmacological and non pharmacological). Midwives acknowledged that women may decline non-pharmacological pain treatment techniques because of inadequate awareness, therefore emphasizing the importance of educating women on this subject. Most of the respondents believed that having some extra staff would assist them in carrying out their responsibilities, managing pain, and supporting women. Participants stated that non-pharmacological pain management approaches are ineffective on their own but considerably more effective if utilized with pharmacological ones. They also advocated for the hiring of doulas and the recruitment of students to assist with non-pharmacological methods.

According to a study conducted by Kidanemariam et al (2020), on the Utilization of nonpharmacological methods and the perceived barriers for adult postoperative pain management by the nurses at selected National Hospitals in Asmara, Eritrea; a quantitative (descriptive cross sectional) approach was used to assess the use of the nonpharmacological methods and perceived barriers among the nurses. The study was carried out in Halibet National Referral Hospital (HNRH), Orotta National Referral Hospital (ONRH) and Sembel Private Hospital (SPH) in Asmara, Eritrea. Out of 159 number of nurses in the postoperative surgical wards and recovery units in the above

mentioned hospitals, 154 nurses met the inclusion criteria. Nurses of all age group, gender, various level of education, currently working in post-operative and recovery units of the three selected hospitals were among the studied group.

Results from this study showed that majority of the study participants were females whose number was 74%. The age of the participants ranged between 20 and 70 years with a median age of 27 years. A good proportion of the nurses (53.2%) were certificate holders with 1 year training. Among the nurses 38.3% had 3 to 5 years of experience of which 48.1% of them had 2 years of surgical care experience. About 57.1% of the participants were from Orotta hospital. More results from this study (details in table 2) revealed that the cognitive behavioral methods, breathing (81.7%), and relaxation (72.1%) techniques were mostly reported to be utilized as ‘nearly Always/always’ where as positive reinforcement (79.3%), Distraction (77.5%), and imagery (70.1) methods were utilized as ‘not at all/seldom’ among the physical methods, alleviating pain by positioning the patient was responded by most (84.4%) of the nurses as ‘nearly always/always’ whereas thermal regulation was the least used. In emotional support, Therapeutic touch was reported as ‘not at all/seldom’ by (32.5%) of the nurses, while comfort and reassurance were used more often at 92.2%. Concerning preparatory information on the cognitive information preparation for procedure and pain medication after the procedure’ were the most commonly addressed items as ‘nearly always/always’ by (95.2%) and (89.8%)of the nurses. Informing patients on the length of the procedure was at 54.4% whereas, the type of anesthesia was at 78.9% being used ‘not at all/ Seldom’. On ways of giving information regarding sensation majority of the nurses (85.7%) responded as ‘nearly always/always’. More results(Table 5) revealed that revealed that nurses older than 40 years had

significantly higher utilization compared to 20–24 years ($p = 0.005$), and 25–29 years ($p = 0.002$). In addition, nurses at associate level had significantly less utilization compared to those at diploma ($p = 0.010$) and degree ($p = 0.020$) level.

According to the findings from this study, the nurses identified various barriers to the implementation of non pharmacological measures in relieving patients' pain which was broadly categorized into three (Table 6): HealthCare System-Related Barriers; Nurses' related Barriers ; and Patient-Related Barriers.

The healthcare system related barriers included; heavy workload, lack of time, lack of administrative support, lack of needed equipment, and lack of pain management policy.

The identified nurse related barriers were; Personal interest, Lack of knowledge regarding non-pharmacological pain relief methods, Lack of experience in using non-pharmacological methods, Personal, traditional and cultural values on pain and pain relief methods, Belief that other health team members should take main role, Belief nurses primary task is to administer pain medication for pain relief, Belief inefficacy of nonpharmacological methods in pain relief.

While for the patient centered barriers, the following were identified; Patients inability to cooperate, Language difference.

According to a study carried out by ALRIMALI et al (2023), on Nonpharmacological Pain Management Practices Among Nurses Working In Multiple centers in Saudi Arabia: A cross-sectional study, it employed a self-reported survey to evaluate the use of nonpharmacological pain management techniques, alongside the factors influencing their use, among a sample of nurses in Hai'l, Saudi Arabia. The purpose of this study was to gain insight into the extent and factors affecting the use of nonpharmacological methods for managing pain among nurses in various

settings. The study was conducted in January 2023. This study was conducted among all registered nurses working in 16 central and peripheral hospitals in Hai'l utilizing nonprobability convenience sampling. The target sample size necessary to achieve the study objectives and sufficient statistical power was calculated using a sample size calculator. The calculator determined that 320 participants were needed, based on a margin of error of 5%, a confidence level of 95%, and an estimated response distribution of 50% from the population of 1899 nurses in 16 hospitals within the Hai'l health cluster. The data for this study were collected through a self-reported web-based questionnaire, which was administered to nurses on a voluntary and anonymous basis.. The results on the demographic characteristics of the participants are as follows; of 324 respondents, of which 74.4% (n = 241) were female and 25.6% (n = 83) were male. The complete data summary on the demographic characteristics is presented in Table 1 of the study.

Moreover results from the study further identified that the nonpharmacological pain management practices score was 2.89 ± 0.48 , suggesting these practices were used, on average, sometimes.

Nonpharmacological pain management differed by gender, with females having a higher score (2.96 ± 0.47) than males (2.68 ± 0.47), $F(1,322) = 20.777$, $P < 0.001$. However, the practices did not significantly vary by age group, educational attainment, years of experience, where knowledge of pain stemmed from, or the amount of pain education received in the last 2 years ($P > 0.05$).

The top five most frequently used practices include putting the patient in a comfortable position, providing a quiet and comfortable room, using comfort devices, counseling and education for the patient/family, and communicating with the patient and family as recorded in Table 2. Results showed that the overall mean barriers score was 3.04 ± 0.65 , indicating a more neutral stance on the subject, on average. Barriers to nonpharmacological pain management were significantly different per hours of pain management education the respondent received within the last 2 years,

$F(3, 320) = 4.578, P = 0.004$ [Figure 1]. Barriers to nonpharmacological pain management practices did not significantly vary by gender, age group, educational attainment, years of experience, nursing specialty area, and where knowledge of pain stemmed from, $P > 0.05$.

The top five identified barriers in descending order are: an insufficient number of nurses per shift, multiple responsibilities, a heavy workload, nurse fatigue, and a chaotic environment as seen in Table 3. Results of the study indicated that there was no significant variation in nursing practices related to nonpharmacological interventions based on demographic factors such as age, level of education, years of experience, and the amount of pain education received in the last 2 years. In the present study, gender did have a statistically significant impact on the results, with female nurses scoring higher than male nurses. Several factors may contribute to the observed disparity in the frequency of nonpharmacological interventions practiced by female and male nurses. One potential explanation is the perpetuation of gender-based stereotypes that women are inherently more compassionate and nurturing, which may result in a greater utilization of nonpharmacological interventions.

In addition, the personal beliefs and values of individual nurses may also play a role in determining the frequency of nonpharmacological interventions utilized. For instance, some female nurses may place a higher emphasis on holistic and patient-centered care, which could contribute to an increased use of such interventions. It is crucial to note that these are merely speculative explanations and that further research is necessary to accurately determine the underlying causes of this observed phenomenon. The most common practices among the study participants include positioning the patient comfortably, a practice that has been widely adopted in the medical community due to its ease of use, acceptability, and minimal time requirements.

Nurses with no recent education on pain management have reported more barriers and the most prevalent barriers identified in the sample were an insufficient number of nurses per shift, multiple responsibilities, a heavy workload, and nurse fatigue. This study utilized a large sample size to ensure sufficient statistical power. The sample was recruited from multiple settings. The self-reported data can be subject to social desirability bias and may not accurately reflect actual practices. A cross-sectional study design also limits the ability to establish causality or temporal relationships between the study variables. The Sample is limited to nurses working in hospitals in Hai'l, SaudinArabia, thereby limiting generalizability to other populations and settings. The study also does not assess the effectiveness of nonpharmacological pain management techniques, only their prevalence, and perceived barriers.

According to a study carried out by Mohamed Bayoumi MM, Khonji LMA and Gabr WFM (2021), on : Are Nurses Utilizing the Non-Pharmacological Pain Management Techniques In Surgical Wards ?; this study aimed to explore the nurses' practice toward using Non-Pharmacological pain management techniques in surgical wards. Data was gathered using modified Non-Pharmacological Methods Questionnaire. The study design entailed using a cross-sectional descriptive research design was used from December 2020 to January 2021. However the setting and sample included a convenience sample of all nurses working in the surgical wards (n = 47) from third-level hospital, El-Mansura University Hospital, Egypt. Inclusion criteria: Both genders; All levels of education (diploma, Technical institute, baccalaureate); All nurses caring for patients undergoing minor and major surgery. Whereas the exclusion criteria were; nurses with less than one year of experience and nurses unwilling to participate. Table 3 of the study describes the nonpharmacological pain techniques that may be utilized without doctor order ". It is evident that the cognitive method that had the highest score was distraction, followed by positive

reinforcement, relaxation, and breathing techniques (68.1%, 53.2%, 36.2%, and 36.2% respectively). While nurses can apply the physical method, a massage, followed by thermal regulation (cold/heat) positioning (29.8%, 21.3%, and 17.0% respectively). Conversely, emotional support is reflected at the highest level among all non-pharmacological techniques (93.6%). Additionally, nurses reported the demonstration rate of non-pharmacological techniques, with the highest rate of demonstration occurring once a month (34%), and one quarter often used once a week (25.5%).

Table 4 of the study displays nurses' perception regarding the application of non-pharmacological pain management to reduce patients' pain as the cognitive-behavioral methods, imagery, distraction technique, and positive reinforcement recorded the highest scores, whereas the nurses like to demonstrate the physical methods as the positioning, massage, and thermal regulation (91.1%, 87.2%, and 72.3% respectively). The relations between non-pharmacological technique scores and nurses' demographic characteristics are shown in "Table 5". Results showed that male gender had a statistically significant association with the cognitive-behavioral methods, patient family involvement, and overall non-pharmacological methods, $t(p)$ 2.324 (0.025), 2.177 (0.035), and 2.315 (0.025). Besides, the age group from 30–39 had the highest mean score of 66.38 ± 11.82 and was statistically significant with physical methods, $F(p)$ 3.462 (0.040). However, the level of education of the nurses with technical institute level was statistically significant with cognitive behavioral methods, whereas the baccalaureate level had the highest mean score in utilizing physical methods and, overall, nonpharmacological methods, $F(p)$ 3.241 (0.031), 4.388 (0.009) and 3.379 (0.027).

Nurses who participated in the study reported that the highest barrier to applying nonpharmacological pain management was lack of time (25.5%), followed by patient

unwillingness (17%) and patient health beliefs (17%), this is illustrated in Figure 1 of the study. Results indicated that nurses recognized the nonpharmacological pain management techniques as less expensive (21%), with fewer side effects than medication (17%), the patient can demonstrate post-discharge (17%) and can be used as a relaxation technique (14.9%). Implementation of effective non-pharmacological management requires knowledgeable, skillful nurses. Many studies have shown that nurses require more knowledge about non-pharmacological management to reduce patients' pain intensity . The present study was carried out on a convenience sample of 47 nurses although not randomly selected which could mean the study's sampling technique would have not been objective enough. This study adopted non-probability convenience sampling, and the study sample size is limited which may limit the generalization of finding beyond the study sample.

According to a study carried out by Shahla Shkak Shareef and Tiran Jamil Piro (2023), on Knowledge, Practices, and Attitudes of Nurses Regarding Nonpharmacological Pain Management in the Midwifery Ward ; the aim of the study was to assess the nurse's knowledge practice and attitude toward non-pharmacological pain management methods in the delivery room in Erbil Governorate, Iraq. In Erbil Governorate, a cross-sectional study was conducted in public and private Hospitals. Data were collected by using a Non-Probability (Purposive Sample) technique. A total of 78 nurses from public and private hospitals in Erbil Governorate participated in the study. Structured questionnaires and an observational checklist were used to collect data and used SPSS version 26 was used to analyze it. The inclusion criteria composed all nurses working in delivery room and exclusion criteria included the nurses who had at least one year of experience in delivery room. Data was collected through an observational checklist and format for a questionnaire. Results as indicated in Table 1 revealed that most of the sample members were in public hospitals

within the category of 39-49 years old, the highest percentage (35.2%), and in private hospitals shows that most of the participants of the sample study were within the category of 28-38 with a percentage of (41.6%). The majority of the sample of the study in both areas (public, private) hospitals was in married marital status, which is about (70.4%, 70.8%). Most of the sample members in public and private hospitals at the level of education hold a secondary school of nursing degree, with a percentage of (25.9% , 25.0%).

The performance of nurses in public hospitals the use of non-medicinal pain methods in the delivery room is as follows: 31.48% at a good level, 35.18% at a fair level and (33.33%) at a poor level, also in private hospitals using non-medicinal pain methods in the delivery room, it was as follows: (41.7%) of nurses were at good level, (25.0 %) at the appropriate level and 33.3% at a poor level. Regarding the practices of nurses in private hospitals, it indicated that the majority of nurses had good practice. This may be due to adequate space, staff, and equipment. Overall, nurse's knowledge (N=27, 50.0%), (N=9, 37.5%) in public and private hospitals was at a good level, and they had a positive attitude (N=32, 59.3%) in public hospitals and a positive attitude (N=14, 58.3%) in private hospitals. But had a fair practice (N=19, 35.18%) in public hospitals and good practice (N=10, 41.7%) in private hospitals towards labor pain and non-pharmacological pain management. This is due to the lack of time, inadequate staff and the great workload of the staff. This study showed that the knowledge of most of the nurses was at a good level, but it was weak in items such as (cold therapy, acupuncture and acupressure technique), as well as majority of them do the following practices: relaxation technique, give psychological support and, ensure that women's relatives are there during the entire labor process; and they do not use other types of non-Pharmacological pain relieving method like: hypnosis, ice packs, intradermal water block. It is required to design a pain-relieving non-pharmacological training course for nurses.

In another study carried out by Timothy Aghogho EHWARIEME, Uzezi JOSIAH and Oluwaseun Oluwafunmilayo ABIODUN on : Postoperative Pain Assessment and Management Among Nurses in selected hospitals in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria; the study was designed to determine the nurse assessment of postoperative pain and its management in selected hospitals, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria. Target population were nurses from nursing officer II to Chief nursing officer cadres who work in the various surgical Wards/units only of the selected health facilities. They were 222. A purposive sampling technique was employed to recruit participants for the study. All the target population who meet the inclusion criteria were used for the study as the target population is small. The inclusion criteria were as follows: those registered with the Nursing and Midwifery Council of Nigeria; an employee of the selected health facilities ; those who have worked in the surgical wards/units of the selected health facility for not <6 months. The exclusion criteria were as follows: those who are sick and are not able to participate and ; those who were on leave of any type approved by the various health facilities.

The results of the study showed that ; providing clean, calm, and well-ventilated ward environment with a mean score of 3.69 ± 0.61 was the most used nonpharmacological method, followed by distraction, relaxation, and guided imagery with a mean score of 3.52 ± 0.50 , dressing, bandage, splint, and reinforce wound sites postoperatively with a mean score of 3.39 ± 0.54 , and early ambulation/exercise” with a mean score of 3.20 ± 0.62 [Figure 2].

This study offers a broad perspective when it comes to patients suitable for nonpharmacological interventions in pain relief because post operative patients are a diverse group and can also include postnatal women who had caesarean sections making it suitable . A limitation is that the study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey design using a self-reported questionnaire as an instrument of data collection which limited to some extent the objectivity of the information

obtained from the participants. It would have been more objective if the researchers adopted an observational technique in collecting the data in which participants are covertly observed to see the different pain assessment tools and pain management techniques applied in postoperative pain management in the different health facilities.

2.3.3 Factors Influencing Nurses' Choices Of Non-Pharmacological Methods Of Pain Management

According to a study carried out by Israa A. M. Abuijlan, Priyalatha Muthu, and Manju Nair Avinash (2023), the aim of the study was to explore the nurses' experience and perceived challenges in using non pharmacological pain measures in caring for patients with musculoskeletal pain. The study was conducted in the medical and orthopedic ward of an accredited government hospital in Ras-Al Khaimah, United Arab Emirates. Eleven nurses who consented to participate were selected using a purposive sampling technique. The target population group was registered nurses with more than 1 year of experience in the orthopedics and medical inpatient units. A total of eleven nurses were interviewed (two males and nine females). Two nurses were interviewed individually daily, and written verbatim and audio recordings were obtained. The interviews were conducted in English language. Each interview lasted between 25 and 35 minutes. The average age of nurses is 29 years (SD =6.3). The average years of nursing experience is 8.45 (SD =8.27) while the years of caring for patients with musculoskeletal pain is 8.27 (SD =3.3). All of the participants have a Bachelor of Science in Nursing degree. None of them have a specific pain management education.

The nurses' utilization of different Non-Pharmacological methods of relieving patients' was changing depending on the following factors; their findings from constant observation and

monitoring, previous experience in utilizing specific NPPCM, the suitability of NPPCM to musculoskeletal diseases, and patients' preferences.

On findings from constant observation and monitoring nurses in the current study mentioned that observing patients' facial expressions and monitoring the severity of pain is essential to determine the use of NPPCM. In this study, nurses applied NPPCM when the patient's facial expression did not reflect severe pain.

Regarding the previous experiences in utilizing specific non pharmacological measures of pain control, a nurse admitted that she noticed that stabilizing the affected limb and applying ice therapy to the fractured part reduced the patient's pain and on encouraging the patients to do breathing exercises, they become more comfortable, also from her experience as part of diversional activities, after taking patients to the hospital's ground floor (garden) during the sunset, they become less complaining.

When it came to the suitability of NPPCM to patients' medical conditions, some nurses reported that the selection of certain interventions depends on the medical diagnosis. For example, NPPCM used for fracture patients is not the same as for patients with back pain and arthritis. In one of the respondents statements, managing lower back pain was better aided by applying a heat compress however for a patient with a fractured limb, stabilizing the affected limb, and applying ice therapy was a preferred choice for the nurse, also arthritis patients were scheduled for physiotherapy to alleviate their pain while patients with muscular spasms were treated by massaging.

One of the nurses mentioned that patients might prefer certain NPPCM over another, which is based on patients' experience and cultural norms, example, Muslim patients prefer to recite or listen to the Quran rather than meditation as the disease gives them way to get closer to Allah and

it is one method of healing. So the personal preferences was also a determining factor on the specific non pharmacological pain relief measures that the nurses implemented in their practice.

According to a study carried out by Wafaa T. Elgzar, Majed S. Alshahrani and Heba A. Ibrahim (2024) on : Non-pharmacological labor pain relieve Methods: utilization and associated factors Among midwives and maternity nurses In Najran, Saudi Arabia.

A cross-sectional research was conducted in Maternal and Children Hospital/Najran, Saudi Arabia, from April to May 2023 and incorporated a convenience sample of 164 midwives and maternity nurses. The data was entered into SPSS version 23, and the necessary analysis was done. Descriptive statistics were used to describe data as numbers, percentages, mean, and standard deviations. This study revealed in its results that one year increase in working experiences increased the nurse probability for higher NPLPR practices by six times [AOR=6.501(1.012–41.764), p=0.049). Also, an increase of one point in the participants' NPLPR attitudes increased the probability of higher application of NPLPR by one time [AOR=1.125(1.013–1.249), P=0.028]. On the other hand, provider: patient ratio of 1:6 [AOR=0.165 (0.055–0.432), p=0.000] or 1:8 [AOR=0.155 (0.046–0.531), P=0.003] decreased the midwife/nurse probability to provide NPLPR when compared to a ratio of 1:4. Furthermore, working for 12 [AOR=0.712 (0.242–2.872), p=0.048] hours or more than 12 h [AOR=0.205 (0.061–0.712), p=0.013] decreased the midwife/nurse probability to utilize NPLPR when taking working for 8 hours as a reference. This study reveals that a higher NPLPR utilization was associated with some demographic characteristics, such as midwives'/nurses' level of education and age, more results pointed out that NPLPR training is one of the facility-related factors affecting NPLPR utilization among midwives and maternity nurses receiving NPLPR training during formal education increased the likelihood of using the NPLPR four times higher than nurses without training. Also in the current study, the

utilization of NPLPR was associated with working experience. This could be attributed to the fact that those serving longer had acquired sufficient knowledge, expertise, and competence to efficiently manage labor using NPLP while low utilization of NPLPR was attributed to an increased patient-provider ratio and working hours. This study showed that an increase of one point in the participants' NPLPR attitudes increased the probability of higher application of NPLPR by one time. This implies that nurses' favorable attitudes toward NPLPR strategies facilitate their higher application in clinical practice, however this is difficult to measure quantitatively and scientifically as it is a subjective factor. The participants found that a positive attitude had significantly associated with higher nonpharmacological pain relief practices.

Therefore, promoting the nurse's attitude toward the impact of NPLPR methods is crucial.

All the factors mentioned above that affect nurses utilization of nonpharmacological pain relief practices also affect their choices of the types they utilize as this is an inherent part of their overall practice in utilizing non pharmacological interventions for patients' pain relief.

According to a study carried out by Eyeberu et al (2022) on : Obstetrics Care Providers Attitude And utilization of Non-Pharmacological Labor Pain Management in Harari regional State Health facilities, Ethiopia; A facility-based cross-sectional study was conducted in Harari regional state health facilities in Ethiopia from May 20 to June 10, 2021 of which the study population consisted of all obstetric care providers working in Harari regional state health facilities during the study period. Because the source population in the study area was small, all obstetric caregivers who were available during the study period were included. Obstetrics care providers who were unable to collect data due to illness, annual leave, or training were excluded from the study. The study was conducted at maternal health facilities including two public hospitals (HFSUH and Jugol hospital), one private hospital (Harar General hospital), two private clinics, and nine Harari

regional state health centers 464 obstetric care providers in all (200 (43.1%) were males and 264 (56.9%) were females which is a 0.76 to 1 male to female ratio. More than half 233 (53%) of the study participants were midwives. Furthermore, the study results showed that variables like age, sex, clinical experience, caregiver preferences, level of education, pain expectation of caregiver, availability of protocols, level of knowledge, and attitude of the respondents towards nonpharmacological labor pain management were associated with simple linear regression analysis. The final multiple linear regression model sex of the respondents, clinical experience, pain expectation, individual preference, attitude, and knowledge of non pharmacological labor pain management were significantly associated with utilization of nonpharmacological labor pain management (pvalue <0.05). This means that the choice of non pharmacological interventions of pain relief which is a component of the overall utilization of these interventions are also hinged on these factors. However, the strength of this study is the use of a larger sample size, but it is limited to labour pain alone hence though the sample size is large, the scope is narrow when compared to non pharmacological interventions that are practicable in a more diverse range of cases and patients. Another limitation is that it might not indicate a cause-effect relationship because the study design was cross-sectional. Since the study is institution-based and did not incorporate women in labor, the results might lack generalization to the entire population in the catchment area.

In another study carried out by Limakatso Elizabeth Parkies, Daphne Murray and Uchenna Benedine Okafor (2024) on : The Benefits and Barriers of Providing Non-Pharmacological Pain Relief to Women in Labour during COVID-19:A Qualitative Study of Midwives in South Africa. In this study, the participants were all black female midwives (n = 10) with extensive professional experience in midwifery (ranging from 3–27 years) and between 28 and 55 years. The participants

had diplomas in Nursing (General, Psychiatry, and Community) and Midwifery. It was a qualitative descriptive study included ten purposively selected midwives who were approached by the principal author to participate in the study. After being informed of the study's objectives and details, only those midwives who expressed their consent to partake in the interviews were granted inclusion. To participate in the study, participants were required to have at least five years of working experience, be employed in maternity units, and sign an informed consent form and participants were interviewed at two district hospitals in Matjhabeng Municipality, Lejweleputswa District, Free State Province of South Africa. The data were analyzed using the Tesch technique.

Results showed that non pharmacological interventions utilized by the midwives included mobilization exercises, warm baths/showers, breathing exercises, and back rubs. The above-cited techniques serve to distract attention from the source of the pain and have a calming effect, as they say stated: Non-pharmacological pain relief is still working like mobilizing the patient, sending the patients to the shower, as well as deep breathing. Statements made by the midwives in the results of this study indicate that factors affecting the utilization of the above mentioned choices of non pharmacological interventions for patients' relief of pain were the global effect of the pandemic COVID 19, the patients' preferences, their cultural backgrounds (as black women here did not usually come with their partners during labor), and lack of the necessary facilities in the healthcare facility for adequate implementation of these measures.

According to the study by Tsegaye et al (2023) ; Non-Pharmacological Pain Management Practice and Associated Factors Among Nurses Working at Comprehensive Specialized Hospitals, in a study intended to assess nonpharmacological pain management practice and associated factors among nurses working at comprehensive specialized hospitals in northwest, Ethiopia.

Stratified random sampling technique was used to select 322 study participants. A binary logistic regression model was used to identify factors associated with non-pharmacological pain management practice, data were checked for completeness and consistency. Then it was coded and entered in EPI data version 3.02 Software. After that, data were exported to SPSS version 25 for analysis. Model fitness test (Goodness of fit was checked with Hosmer Lemeshow model of fit [P = .36] and assumption test for multi-collinearity problem [VIF < 3.35] was done).

Results from the study as illustrated in Table 4 shows the variables affecting or influencing nurses' utilization of nonpharmacological interventions in patient's pain relief , they include; Previous education on NPPM methods, Availability of pain assessment tools in working unit, Type of assessment tool available, Availability of NPPM Guidelines, Availability of NPPM equipment, Workload, Pain severity and the Patient's preferences all has influence on the nurses' utilization of these non pharmacological interventions.

The non pharmacological interventions utilized in this study as illustrated in Table 3 are : Use hot/cold application, applying position changes, applying breathing techniques, movement restrictions/rest, therapeutic communion, providing education to patients, using comfort devices, creating comfortable environment, use of relaxation, use of distraction, application of massage and therapeutic touch.

Further results as seen in Table 2 highlighted socio-demographic factors of the nurses that also affected their utilization of non pharmacological interventions of patients' pain relief, these are: age, sex, level of education , marital status, and work experience.

In another study carried out by OJO Eunice Abimbola, and APATA Helen Olawunmi (2021) : A Survey of Nurses Knowledge and Utilization of Non-Pharmacological Methods of Pain Control at

Two Selected Hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria; it was a cross sectional descriptive study design was used for this research on Nurses knowledge and utilization of non-pharmacological method of pain control in two selected Hospitals in Ibadan, Oyo state. The target populations for this study were trained clinical nurses working in surgical, medical departments. They were drawn from all cadres of nurses ranging from nursing officer 2 to Chief Nursing Officer at Adeoyo State Hospital, Ring road and Oluyoro Catholic Hospital, Oke Ofa, Ibadan, Oyo State. The sample size for this study was one hundred and sixtynine (152) nurses.. The Questionnaire was used to collect the relevant data and it was scrutinized by the expert in Tests and Measurement for clarification, evaluation of items and assessment of content validity.

Results from Table 7 revealed that there is significant relationship between knowledge and utilization of non-pharmacological methods of pain control among nurses in the two selected hospitals in Ibadan, it reveals that $r= 0.35$: $p<0.05$. The null hypothesis is hereby rejected while those from Table 8 reveals that there is significant relationship between attitude and utilization of non-pharmacological methods of pain control in the two selected hospitals in Ibadan, it reveals that $r= 0.62$: $p<0.05$. The null hypothesis is hereby rejected. The study found statistically significant associations between some of the background factors and the utilization of methods, the background factors that proved to be influential in the utilization of non-pharmacological methods in all of these international studies were age, job title and nursing experience. The barriers would also be a determinant to whether the nurses would implement non pharmacological practices or which of them they would most likely implement, barriers to the use of non-pharmacological method of pain control included: Excess workload 100% and lack of time 76.9%. Even when the nurse may be supportive of the use of nonpharmacological therapies their use of these therapies were counterbalanced by perceived restrictions of lack of time, 99.4% of the respondents also

reported shortage of nursing staff, patients not cooperating when using the methods 98.8%, When pain is too severe 92.9%, lack of equipment and critical thinking required 91.7% as additional barriers to implementation of non-pharmacological methods.

2.4 SUMMARY OF LITERATURE REVIEW

The various non pharmacological interventions that can be utilized in patients' pain relief by nurses and also midwives and other healthcare providers were identified in various studies carried out in different parts of the world, meaning that it has always been a common practice although increasing attention on this topic only came about over the years. The utilization of these methods, the benefits involved in it as well as the barriers faced in utilizing them (which included the health facility based, the nurses' centered, the patient centered), the limitations of nonpharmacological interventions in managing pain as well as the factors influencing the choices of nonpharmacological interventions utilized by the nurses were all analyzed critically . The literature also examined the Comfort Theory as it relates to the study.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter will be discussed under the following subheadings: Research design, Research setting, Target population, Sample size, Sampling technique, Instrument for data collection, Validity of instruments, Reliability of instruments, Ethical consideration, Method of data collection and Method of data analysis.

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

A descriptive cross-sectional research design was adopted for this study. This is because it would help the researcher to have adequate information regarding the research problem within the available time.

3.1 RESEARCH SETTING

The research setting is the physical location and conditions in which data collection takes place in the study. This is also seen as the physical, social and cultural site in which the researcher conducts the study.

This study was carried out among Nurses working in selected wards (Male Medical , Female Medical, Male Surgical, Female Surgical, Oncology/Hematological, Labour Ward, orthopedic, intensive care unit, pediatric and emergency) in the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, Edo State Nigeria. Geographically, the University of Benin Teaching Hospital is located in Egor LGA, Benin City. University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH) is a premier and multi-specialty healthcare service provider in West Africa. The hospital was founded on May 12th, 1973 as a result

of the Nigerian National Health Act's edict number 12, which was passed into law. The UBTH of today boasts a bed capacity of over 860 as of August 2017 and still increasing with a multitude of departments offering a wide range of services, all of which combined to make the Institution the Centre of Excellence as it stands today. The UBTH originally had a bed capacity of 360 when it was officially opened on May 12th, 1973. It also sponsors research opportunities for university lecturers and other interested parties with economic morbidity burden as research issues, and it provides the facilities required for educating high and middle level personnel for the healthcare industry. The nearby communities are also given access to some primary healthcare options by UBTH through the Community Health Centres in Ogbona and Udo and the General Practice Clinic that came on stream later.

3.3 TARGET POPULATION

The target population for this study was 169 participants which comprised of both male and female nurses of different hierarchies who were working in ten selected wards in the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, Edo State. These wards are the male and female medical wards, male and female surgical wards, oncology/hematological ward, pediatric, emergency, orthopedic, intensive care unit and labour ward.

Table 3.1 Study of the target population

Name Of Ward	Number Of Male nurses	Number Of female nurses	Total
Male medical	1	15	16
Female medical	1	18	19
Male surgical	—	16	16
Female Surgical	—	14	14
Oncology/hematological ward	1	14	15
Labour	—	20	20
Male Orthopedic	—	20	20
Emergency department	3	16	19
Intensive Care Unit	1	14	15
Female Orthopedic	—	15	15
			169

(Statistics from each Ward manager, August 2024)

3.4 SAMPLE SIZE

The sampling size is the number of subjects or participants required and to which the study findings will be generalized.

The sample size was estimated from a population of 169 respondents using the Taro Yamane (1967) formula .

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e^2)}$$

Where; n = sample

N = population size

e = margin of error (level of precision 5% or 0.05)

Thus; since N =

$$n = 169 / [1 + 169 \times 0.05^2]$$

$$n = 169 / [1 + 0.4225]$$

$$n = 169 / [1.4225]$$

$$n = 118$$

10% attrition = 12

Therefore, the minimum sample size is 118 + 12 = 130

Criteria for Sample Selection

- 1. Inclusion criteria;** nurses who were willing to participate in the study nurses who are in the selected wards of study population nurses who has had at least six months of working experience in the ward

2. **Exclusion criteria;** nurses who did not consent to be part of the study
professional care givers who were not nurses such as doctors, midwives.

3.5 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The sampling technique used for this study was the Purposive Sampling technique. It is a non probability sampling technique in which, the researcher intentionally selects or hand picks participants based on specific characteristics or criteria that are relevant to the research purpose. The sample was chosen because the individuals have particular knowledge, experiences, or traits that are valuable for the study (Purposive) and also in the ratio corresponding to the number of participants in each Ward (Proportional). Example: In a study about expert opinions on nursing, a researcher may choose only senior nurses with at least 10 years of experience.

Now in this study, this is very much suitable because one of the inclusion criteria for sample selection is that the nurses must have had at least six months of working experience.

3.6 INSTRUMENT FOR DATA COLLECTION

A self- structured questionnaire was utilized for data collection in this study. This was constructed in both closed and open-ended form where the respondents' will be asked both to tick appropriately the option that suits their best knowledge and practices and to write out or specify their own perceptions, practices and experience which is not inherent of the questionnaire design in provided spaces in the questionnaire.

The questionnaires were divided into section A, B, C, and D to address the research objectives under investigation.

Section A: accesses the socio-demographic data of the respondents

Section B: accesses the different types of non pharmacological interventions utilized by the respondents of in relieving patients' pain

Section C: accesses the respondents' utilization of nonpharmacological measures in relieving patients' pain (frequency of use)

Section D: accesses the factors that influences the various choices of various non pharmacological interventions utilized by respondents in relieving patients' pain as well as the perceived barriers encountered in the utilization process .

3.7 VALIDITY OF INSTRUMENTS

Validity refers to the degree to which a research instrument measures what it intends to measure. The questionnaire adopted was properly structured, organized and simplified by the researcher under the guidance of the researcher's supervisor, a biostatistician before it is distributed . Also face and content validity was carried out.

3.8 RELIABILITY OF INSTRUMENTS

Reliability refers to the degree to which assessment tool produces stable and consistent result. A reliable instrument is one that came produce the same results if behavior is measured again by the same scale (Colin and Julie 2006). A reliability test was conducted using Cronbach's Alpha. This was after a pilot study, carried out at the University of Benin Teaching Hospital (UBTH) with a sample size of 130 nurses, their use of non-pharmacological interventions for pain management was assessed. The researcher did this by distributing 13 questionnaires among the nurses in the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, thereby utilizing 10% of the sample size for this test. The Cronbach's Alpha value obtained was 0.71, indicating an acceptable reliability. This suggests that the research instrument was reliable for measuring

the intended variables, ensuring that the responses were consistent and dependable for the study's objectives. This reliability test confirms the credibility of the data collected, supporting the validity of the study's findings on nurses' use of non-pharmacological pain relief methods.

3.9 METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

130 well structured questionnaires containing questions relating to the research study was self administered to the sample at the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, Edo State. While this was taking place, they were guided on how to answer the questions. The researcher approached each nurse, explored research and the aim of the study, then sought consent from each nurse for their participation in the study. All respondents will be assured of their confidentiality and anonymity. The researcher was present during the process of filling of the questionnaires by the respondents and immediately this is completed by each respondent, the researcher retrieves the questionnaires.

3.10 METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

This study employed the use of descriptive statistics using mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage distribution, while the Chi-square statistical analysis techniques was used to test the research hypothesis with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 29. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

3.11 ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

The researcher obtained ethical approval from the office of the research and ethical committee in the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, Benin City, before carrying out this study in the facility.

The researcher is aware of the ethical and moral principles that regulate the collection of information from respondents and the major ethical principles upheld in this study are:

1. **Autonomy:** The respondents participation in this study is solely based on their choice and decisions, nobody will be coerced or forced into being part of this study.
2. **Informed consent:** the researcher will make sure that the participants receive full explanation of the what the study is all about, it's objectives and ensure that there is full understanding on the part of the respondents before proceeding to collect data .
3. **Maintenance of confidentiality:** all through this study, there will be no disclosure of personal information of the respondents such as names, phone numbers , address and others. This will be maintained by ensuring only the supervisor and statistician have access to these data.
4. **Right to fair treatment:** all participants will be treated equally, there will be no form of discrimination or favoritism in this study.
5. **Freedom from exploitation:** In this study, the participants will be assured by the researcher that none of the information from this study will be used against them . The issue of financial exploitation is also prevented none of the participants will be charged any fee for partaking in this study.
6. **Avoidance of plagiarism:** the researcher ensures that all authors used in this study are accurately cited both in text and in the reference list.

CHAPTER FOUR
RESULTS

Table 4.1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Frequency (n = 129)	Percent (%)
Age		
21-30 years	41	31.8
31-40 years	39	30.2
41-50 years	28	21.7
51 years and above	21	16.3
Marital Status		
Single	53	41.1
Married	75	51.2
Divorced	1	0.78
Educational Background		
OND	18	14
HND	23	17.8
BNSc	47	36.4
MSN	21	16.3
DNP	8	6.2
Others	12	9.3
Religion		
Christian	99	76.7
Muslim	25	19.4
Pagan	0	0
Others	5	3.9
Designation		
NOII	31	24
NOI	27	20.9
SNO	22	17.1
PNO	16	12.4
ACNO	15	11.6
CNO	11	8.5
ADNS	7	5.4
Years of Working Experience		
0-5 yrs	26	20.2
6-10 yrs	33	25.6
11-15 yrs	24	18.6
16-20 yrs	20	15.5
21-25 yrs	14	10.9
26 yrs and above	12	9.3
Highest Educational Qualification in Nursing		
Bachelor Degree (B.Sc.)	58	45
Master	39	30.2
Ph.D.	12	9.3
Others	20	15.5
Professional Qualification		
RN	45	34.9
RM	33	25.6
RNM	24	18.6
RPN	8	6.2
RPON	7	5.4
RAEN	6	4.7
Others	6	4.7

Table 4.1 provides an overview of the socio-demographic characteristics of 129 respondents. The majority of respondents were aged 21-30 years (31.8%) and 31-40 years (30.2%), while a smaller portion were aged 51 years and above (16.3%). Most respondents were married (51.2%), with others being single (41.1%) or divorced (0.78%). In terms of education, 36.4% held a Bachelor of Nursing Science (BNSc), followed by 17.8% with a Higher National Diploma (HND) and 16.3% with a Master of Science in Nursing (MSN). Regarding religion, Christians made up the majority (76.7%), followed by Muslims (19.4%). Respondents' professional designations varied, with the largest groups being Nursing Officers II (NOII) (24%) and Nursing Officers I (NOI) (20.9%), while smaller proportions were Chief Nursing Officers (CNO) (8.5%) and Assistant Directors of Nursing Services (ADNS) (5.4%). Most respondents had 6-10 years of working experience (25.6%), with fewer having 0-5 years (20.2%). The highest educational qualifications were primarily at the Bachelor's level (45%), followed by Master's (30.2%) and Doctoral (9.3%). For professional qualifications, the majority were Registered Nurses (RN) (34.9%), followed by Registered Midwives (RM) (25.6%) and Registered Nurse Midwives (RNM) (18.6%), indicating a broad range of professional expertise among the respondents.

Answering Research Questions

Research Question 1: What are the various non pharmaceutical measures that nurses utilize in managing patients pain in UBTH?

Table 4.2: Different types of nonpharmacological measures utilized by nurses in patients' pain relief in UBTH

Nonpharmacological Measure	Yes	No	Mean	Remark
Massage	102 (79.1)	27 (20.9)	1.8	Utilized
Hot/Cold compress	95 (73.6)	34 (26.4)	1.7	Utilized
Distraction techniques	78 (60.5)	51 (39.5)	1.6	Utilized
Reassurance and emotional support	105 (81.4)	24 (18.6)	1.8	Utilized
Deep breathing technique	88 (68.2)	41 (31.8)	1.7	Utilized
Repositioning of patients	90 (69.8)	39 (30.2)	1.7	Utilized
Reading of Bible, Quran, or other spiritual/religious practices such as prayers	62 (48.1)	67 (51.9)	1.5	Utilized
Presence of family and loved ones around my patients during pain	85 (65.9)	44 (34.1)	1.7	Utilized
Simple comfort devices such as pillows, special mattress, air rings, etc.	79 (61.2)	50 (38.8)	1.6	Utilized
Patient education and counseling	98 (76.0)	31 (24.0)	1.8	Utilized
Limiting patients' movements to reduce pain	28(21.7)	101(78.3)	1.2	Non-utilizes
	Grand Mean		1.6	

Mean Cut-off = 1.5

Table 4.2 shows the utilization of various nonpharmacological measures for pain relief among patients at UBTH. Commonly used interventions included reassurance and emotional support

(81.4%), massage (79.1%), and patient education and counseling (76.0%), each with a mean of 1.8. Other frequently utilized methods were hot/cold compress (73.6%), deep breathing (68.2%), and repositioning of patients (69.8%). Measures involving family presence (65.9%) and simple comfort devices like pillows and special mattresses (61.2%) were also commonly applied. Religious or spiritual practices were used by nearly half (48.1%) of respondents. In contrast, limiting patient movement was less frequently employed (21.7%) and was considered non-utilized based on a mean cut-off of 1.5. The grand mean of 1.6 indicates a generally high usage of nonpharmacological pain management measures.

Figure 4.1: Pie chart showing different types of nonpharmacological measures utilized by nurses in patients' pain relief

The pie chart indicates that 83 (64.3%) nurses utilize non-pharmacological measures for pain relief in patients, whereas 46 (35.7%) do not employ these measures.

Research Question 2: How often do nurses utilize these non pharmaceutical measures of pain relief in UBTH ?

Table 4.3: Nurses' utilization of non-pharmacological measures of pain relief

Measure Utilized	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Not at all	Mean	Remark
Massage	79 (61.2)	33 (25.6)	13 (10.1)	4 (3.1)	1	3.4	Utilized
Hot/Cold compress	68 (52.7)	37 (28.7)	18 (14.0)	6 (4.7)	5	3.3	Utilized
Distraction techniques	61 (47.3)	43 (33.3)	22 (17.1)	3 (2.3)	1	3.3	Utilized
Reassurance and emotional support	84 (65.1)	30 (23.3)	12 (9.3)	3 (2.3)	2	3.5	Utilized
Deep breathing technique	72 (55.8)	34 (26.4)	17 (13.2)	6 (4.7)	0	3.3	Utilized
Repositioning of patients	78 (60.5)	33 (25.6)	15 (11.6)	3 (2.3)	1	3.4	Utilized
Reading of Bible, Quran, or other spiritual/religious practices such as prayers	29 (22.5)	31 (24.0)	45 (34.9)	24 (18.6)	9	2.5	Utilized
Presence of family and loved ones around my patients during pain	90 (69.8)	30 (23.3)	6 (4.7)	3 (2.3)	1	3.6	Utilized
Simple comfort devices such as pillows, special mattress, air rings, etc.	81 (62.8)	32 (24.8)	12 (9.3)	4 (3.1)	2	3.5	Utilized
Patient education and counseling	83 (64.3)	37 (28.7)	7 (5.4)	2 (1.6)	1	3.6	Utilized
Limiting patients' movements to reduce pain	7 (5.4)	15 (11.6)	28 (21.7)	79 (61.2)	32	1.6	Non-utilized
						Grand Mean	3.2

Mean Cut-off = 2.5

Table 4.3 highlights the extent of nurses' utilization of non-pharmacological pain relief measures. Key interventions consistently used include the presence of family and loved ones (69.8% always, mean 3.6), patient education and counseling (64.3% always, mean 3.6), and reassurance and emotional support (65.1% always, mean 3.5). Massage (61.2% always, mean 3.4), simple comfort devices like pillows (62.8% always, mean 3.5), and repositioning of patients (60.5% always, mean 3.4) were also prevalent. Moderate use was noted for distraction techniques (47.3% always, mean 3.3) and deep breathing techniques (55.8% always, mean 3.3). Spiritual practices had a varied application, with only 22.5% utilizing them always (mean 2.5). Limiting patient movements was least utilized, with only 5.4% always applying this method, reflected in a low mean of 1.6. Overall, the grand mean of 3.2 indicates high use of diverse non-pharmacological pain management techniques among nurses.

Figure 4.2: Bar chart showing nurses' utilization of non-pharmacological measures of pain relief

The bar chart illustrates that 99 (76.7%) nurses utilize non-pharmacological measures for pain relief, while 30 (23.3%) do not employ these methods.

Research Question 3: What are the factors that influence the choice of various non pharmaceutical methods used by nurses in UBTH for patients’ pain relief?

Table 4.4: Factors influencing the choices of non-pharmacological interventions utilized by nurses in pain relief

Factor Influencing Choice	Yes	No	Mean	Remark
Time constraint	82 (63.6)	47 (36.4)	1.6	Influential
Lack of necessary equipment	77 (59.7)	52 (40.3)	1.6	Influential
Special training in non-pharmacological pain relief measures	89 (69.0)	40 (31.0)	1.7	Influential
Heavy workload on nurses	93 (72.1)	36 (27.9)	1.7	Influential
Beliefs of the patient	70 (54.3)	59 (45.7)	1.5	Influential
Beliefs of the nurse	85 (65.9)	44 (34.1)	1.7	Influential
Personal preferences of the patient	79 (61.2)	50 (38.8)	1.6	Influential
Healthcare institution policy and practices	94 (72.9)	35 (27.1)	1.7	Influential
	Grand Mean		1.6	

Mean Cut-off = 1.5

Table 4.4 identifies key factors influencing nurses' selection of non-pharmacological pain relief interventions. The most influential factors include healthcare institution policies and practices (72.9%), heavy workload (72.1%), and specialized training in non-pharmacological methods

(69.0%), each with a mean of 1.7. Time constraints (63.6%), nurses' personal beliefs (65.9%), and patients' preferences (61.2%) also significantly affected choices, with mean scores between 1.5 and 1.7. Additionally, limited equipment (59.7%) and patient beliefs (54.3%) were noted as influential. With an overall grand mean of 1.6, these findings underscore multiple logistical, personal, and institutional factors shaping nurses' application of non-pharmacological pain relief strategies.

Figure 4.3: Pie chart showing factors influencing the choices of non-pharmacological interventions utilized by nurses in pain relief

The pie chart indicates that 84 (65.1%) nurses find factors influencing their choices of non-pharmacological interventions to be influential, whereas 45 (34.9%) consider these factors non-influential.

Table 4.5: Relationship between the years of working experience or hierarchical status of nurses and their utilization of non-pharmaceutical measures in relieving patients' pain.

types of nonpharmacological measures	utilization of non pharmaceutical measures		Test Statistics (χ^2)	df	P value	Decision
	Utilized	Non-utilized				
Utilized	19 (47.6)	59(52.4)	9.682	1	0.09	Accepted
Non-utilized	33 (73.2)	18 (26.8)				

Table 4.5 reveals no significant relationship between nurses' years of working experience or hierarchical status and their use of non-pharmaceutical measures for pain relief. Of the nurses using non-pharmacological methods, 47.6% actively utilized these measures, while 52.4% did not. Among those not using non-pharmacological measures, 73.2% also refrained from their utilization, with only 26.8% using them occasionally. The chi-square test ($\chi^2 = 9.682$, $df = 1$, $p = 0.09$) supports this conclusion, as the p-value indicates no significant association between experience or status and the use of non-pharmaceutical pain management approaches.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This chapter discusses the major findings of the research compared with the literature reviewed, the implication for nursing, summary, conclusion, Recommendations and Suggestions for further Studies.

5.1. Discussion of major Findings

The study assessed the use of nonpharmacological measures in the relief of patients' pain by nurses in a tertiary health institution. The study revealed diverse socio-demographic characteristics among the nursing respondents, which provides important context for understanding the workforce composition and its potential influence on non-pharmacological pain management practices. Age distribution showed a relatively young workforce, with 62% of respondents under 40 years (31.8% aged 21-30 years and 30.2% aged 31-40 years). This age profile aligns with Eyeberu et al.'s, 2022 findings, which identified age as a significant factor associated with non-pharmacological pain management practices. Similarly, Wafaa T. Elgzar et al, 2024 found that nurses' age was among the demographic characteristics associated with higher utilization of non-pharmacological pain relief methods. Educational qualifications demonstrated a well-educated nursing workforce, with 36.4% holding BNSc degrees and 16.3% having MSN qualifications. This educational profile supports Wafaa T. Elgzar et al.'s, 2024 findings that higher education levels were associated with increased utilization of non-pharmacological pain relief methods. The presence of advanced degree holders (6.2% DNP) suggests potential for evidence-based practice implementation, though none of the participants in Abuijlan et al.'s, 2023 study had specific pain management education despite all having BSN degrees. Work experience distribution showed varied levels of clinical exposure, with 25.6% having 6-10 years of experience, followed by 20.2% with 0-5 years. This experience

range is particularly relevant given Wafaa T. Elgzar et al.'s , 2024 finding that each year of working experience increased the probability of higher non-pharmacological pain relief practices by six times. Similarly, Tsegaye et al., 2023 identified work experience as a significant factor in non-pharmacological pain management practices. Professional qualifications showed diversity, with 34.9% being Registered Nurses (RN) and 25.6% Registered Midwives (RM). This mix of specializations aligns with Parkies et al.'s, 2024 study of midwives, which emphasized how professional background influences pain management approaches. The variety of specializations (including RPN, RPN, and RAEN) suggests diverse clinical perspectives in pain management approaches. The designation distribution revealed a hierarchical structure with NOII (24%) and NOI (20.9%) forming the largest groups, followed by SNO (17.1%). This staffing pattern relates to OJO and APATA's, 2021 findings about workload distribution and its impact on non-pharmacological pain management implementation. Marital status showed a relatively even distribution between single (41.1%) and married (51.2%) respondents, while religious affiliation indicated a predominantly Christian workforce (76.7%). These demographic characteristics, while not directly addressed in the cited studies, may influence cultural competency in pain management approaches, as suggested by Abuijlan et al.'s, 2023 findings regarding the importance of cultural and religious considerations in pain management choices. This demographic profile suggests a workforce with diverse educational backgrounds and experience levels, which could influence the implementation of non-pharmacological pain management strategies. The relatively young age profile, combined with high educational qualifications, suggests potential for innovative pain management approaches, while the varied experience levels indicate a blend of fresh perspectives and established expertise in clinical practice.

Various non pharmaceutical measures implemented by nurses in managing patients' pain

The findings reveal that a significant proportion (64.3%) of nurses employ non-pharmacological measures for pain management, which aligns with several previous studies. The utilization of these measures varies in frequency and type, with some techniques being more commonly implemented than others. Reassurance and emotional support emerged as the most frequently utilized non-pharmacological intervention (81.4%), followed by massage (79.1%) and patient education and counseling (76.0%). This finding corresponds with Umar et al.'s , 2023 study in Kano State, where reassurance was utilized by 70.6% of respondents. Similarly, the high utilization of massage aligns with their findings where 63.5% of nurses practiced massage techniques. Hot/cold compress therapy showed substantial utilization (73.6%), which correlates with findings from Israa et al.'s 2023 study in the UAE, where nurses regularly employed heat compress for lower back pain and ice therapy for fractured limbs. Deep breathing techniques and repositioning of patients were also widely implemented (68.2% and 69.8% respectively), supporting Aster Shiferaw et al.'s (2020) findings where breathing techniques and patient positioning were among the recognized pain management methods. The presence of family and loved ones (65.9%) and the use of simple comfort devices (61.2%) were moderately utilized, reflecting similar findings in Umar et al.'s (2023) study where 49.4% of nurses involved patients' families in pain management. Distraction techniques showed notable implementation (60.5%), though lower than some studies' findings, such as Ehwarieme et al.'s study where distraction was among the most preferred methods. Interestingly, spiritual/religious practices showed moderate utilization (48.1%), an aspect not prominently featured in many of the referenced studies. The least utilized measure was limiting patients' movements (21.7%), which contrasts with Shegaw Zeleke et al.'s (2021) study where 21.9% of nurses applied movement restriction. These findings demonstrate that nurses employ a

diverse range of non-pharmacological pain management techniques, though the utilization rates vary. This variation might be attributed to factors such as knowledge levels, institutional policies, and cultural contexts, as suggested by multiple studies in different geographical locations.

Utilization of non pharmaceutical measures by nurses in the management of patients' pain

The findings align with and expand upon previous research. The data shows that 76.7% of nurses utilize non-pharmacological measures for pain relief, which is consistent with findings from Kidanemariam et al. (2020) and ALRIMALI et al. (2023). The most frequently utilized measures include presence of family and loved ones (69.8% "always"), reassurance and emotional support (65.1% "always"), and patient education and counseling (64.3% "always"). This aligns with Parkies, Murray, and Okafor's (2024) findings where midwives emphasized the importance of companions and emotional support in pain management. Similarly, ALRIMALI et al. (2023) identified patient/family communication and education among their top five most frequently used practices. Physical interventions such as massage (61.2% "always"), repositioning (60.5% "always"), and hot/cold compress (52.7% "always") were also commonly utilized. This corresponds with Kidanemariam et al.'s (2020) findings where positioning was reported by 84.4% of nurses as being used "nearly always/always." Deep breathing techniques, utilized "always" by 55.8% of nurses in the current study, also mirror Kidanemariam's findings where breathing exercises were used by 81.7% of nurses. The use of comfort devices such as pillows and special mattresses (62.8% "always") aligns with ALRIMALI et al.'s (2023) findings where comfort devices were among the top five most frequently used interventions. Notably, limiting patients' movements was the least utilized measure (mean score 1.6), suggesting nurses recognize the importance of mobilization in pain management, as supported by Parkies, Murray, and Okafor's (2024) study where mobilization was identified as a beneficial pain management strategy. The

overall grand mean of 3.2 (above the 2.5 cut-off) indicates that nurses generally utilize these non-pharmacological measures frequently, demonstrating their integration into routine pain management practices. This comprehensive approach to pain management reflects the evolving understanding of pain relief strategies in nursing practice.

Factors which influence the choice of various non pharmaceutical methods used in pain management by nurses

The study findings reveal that multiple factors influence nurses' choices of non-pharmacological pain management methods, with 65.1% of nurses acknowledging these factors as influential in their practice. This high percentage underscores the significant role various factors play in clinical decision-making regarding pain management interventions. Healthcare institution policies and practices emerged as the most influential factor (72.9%), aligning with findings from Tsegaye et al. (2023), who emphasized the importance of organizational guidelines and protocols in non-pharmacological pain management practices. This institutional influence demonstrates how organizational framework shapes clinical practice decisions. Heavy workload on nurses (72.1%) was identified as another significant factor, supporting the findings of Wafaa T. Elgzar et al. (2024), who found that increased provider-to-patient ratios and extended working hours negatively impacted the utilization of non-pharmacological pain relief methods. This correlation between workload and practice choices was similarly observed in OJO and APATA's (2021) study, where 100% of respondents cited excess workload as a barrier to implementing non-pharmacological methods. Special training in non-pharmacological pain relief measures (69.0%) emerged as influential, corresponding with Elgzar et al.'s (2024) finding that nurses with formal training were four times more likely to utilize non-pharmacological pain relief methods. This highlights the

crucial role of education and training in expanding nurses' pain management repertoire. Nurses' beliefs (65.9%) and time constraints (63.6%) were also significant factors. These findings align with Eyeberu et al.'s, 2022 study, which identified caregiver preferences and attitudes as key determinants in pain management choices. Time constraints as a barrier is consistent with OJO and APATA's (2021) findings, where 76.9% of nurses cited lack of time as a significant obstacle. Patient preferences (61.2%) and equipment availability (59.7%) were identified as influential factors, supporting Abuijlan et al.'s, 2023 observations regarding the importance of patient preferences and cultural norms in pain management choices. The impact of equipment availability aligns with Parkies et al.'s 2024 findings regarding facility infrastructure's role in pain management decisions. Patient beliefs (54.3%), while scoring lowest among the factors, still emerged as influential, supporting Abuijlan et al.'s, 2023 findings about the role of cultural and religious beliefs in pain management choices, particularly noted in their observation of Muslim patients' preferences for Quran recitation over meditation. These findings demonstrate the complex interplay of organizational, personal, and practical factors that influence nurses' choices in non-pharmacological pain management. The results suggest that effective implementation of non-pharmacological pain management requires a comprehensive approach that addresses institutional support, workload management, adequate training, and consideration of both nurse and patient preferences and beliefs.

Hypothesis

In analyzing the findings presented in Table 4.5, it appears that there is no statistically significant relationship between the years of working experience or hierarchical status of nurses and their utilization of non-pharmacological pain management measures ($\chi^2 = 9.682$, $df = 1$, $P = 0.09$). This finding suggests that a nurse's level of experience or hierarchical rank within the healthcare setting does not necessarily determine their likelihood of employing non-pharmaceutical methods to relieve pain. This observation contrasts with some previous studies, such as those by Wafaa T. Elgzar et al. (2024) and Tsegaye et al. (2023), which highlighted a positive correlation between years of experience and higher utilization of non-pharmacological methods. These studies suggested that with each year of experience, nurses are more likely to develop competency in these techniques, potentially due to greater clinical exposure and familiarity with a variety of pain management approaches. The lack of a similar relationship in the present study could indicate that factors other than experience or rank, such as institutional culture, training in specific pain management techniques, and workload, may play a more prominent role in influencing the use of non-pharmacological interventions. Additionally, Eyeberu et al. (2022) identified age as a significant factor associated with the use of non-pharmacological pain management strategies. However, the current study's findings did not find a significant link between professional experience and intervention use, suggesting that younger nurses or those with less tenure might feel equally comfortable employing these methods as their more experienced counterparts. This result could indicate that educational and training programs in the institution may be providing nurses across all experience levels with sufficient competence and confidence to implement these pain management techniques. The finding that hierarchical status is not associated with the utilization of non-pharmacological measures also provides insight into the institutional approach

to pain management. In some healthcare settings, such as those described by OJO and APATA (2021), workload and administrative role expectations influenced nurses' ability to carry out certain types of pain management techniques, particularly time-intensive ones like massage or deep breathing exercises. However, the current study's lack of a hierarchical influence on pain management utilization may reflect a supportive environment that encourages nurses, regardless of rank, to employ a full spectrum of patient care strategies based on the patient's needs rather than their role within the healthcare system.

5.2 Implication To Nursing

The findings from this study highlight several critical implications for nursing practice in the management of patient pain through non-pharmaceutical measures. As more nurses recognize and apply non-pharmacological pain management techniques, it emphasizes the profession's shift toward a holistic, patient-centered approach to care. By understanding the efficacy and importance of interventions like reassurance, massage, and patient education, nurses are empowered to address pain management beyond medication alone, providing patients with a greater sense of comfort and control over their pain experience. This comprehensive approach not only improves patient satisfaction but also reinforces the nurse-patient relationship, enhancing trust and promoting healing.

However, the variability in the application of these measures due to factors like workload, institutional policies, and training availability suggests a need for healthcare facilities to support nurses with adequate resources, structured protocols, and ongoing training. Institutional support for non-pharmacological pain management would enable nurses to overcome barriers like time constraints and heavy patient loads, creating an environment that encourages personalized, empathetic care. Additionally, ensuring that nurses are equipped with the knowledge and skills to

adapt these techniques to each patient's unique needs fosters a culture of individualized care that can be especially beneficial for diverse patient populations with varying pain management preferences.

In light of these findings, the importance of professional development cannot be understated. Training programs focused on non-pharmacological pain relief techniques could not only enhance the effectiveness of nurses' pain management strategies but also empower them to integrate these techniques confidently and consistently into their practice. This continued professional growth, paired with supportive institutional policies, could position non-pharmacological pain management as a central aspect of patient care in nursing, improving outcomes and aligning with modern, evidence-based nursing practices.

5.3 Limitation to the Study

Self-Reported Data: Data were collected through self-reported measures, which could lead to social desirability bias, as participants may have over- or under-reported their use of non-pharmaceutical pain management methods or influencing factors.

5.4 Summary

This study examines the knowledge, strategies, and factors influencing nurses' use of non-pharmacological interventions in managing patient pain, offering insight into how these approaches are applied in clinical settings. Findings reveal that a majority of nurses (64.3%) routinely implement various non-pharmacological pain management techniques, with reassurance, massage, and patient education being the most frequently used. Other strategies like deep breathing, repositioning, and hot/cold compresses were also widely employed, reflecting an emphasis on patient-centered care that aligns with contemporary nursing practices.

The study highlights how institutional policies, workload, and training levels significantly influence nurses' choice of pain management techniques. Institutional guidelines often shape the use of specific methods, while high workloads and time constraints can act as barriers. Additionally, specialized training in non-pharmacological techniques emerged as a key factor, with nurses who had received such training being more likely to use a broader range of pain management approaches. Other factors such as nurse and patient beliefs, patient preferences, and equipment availability also played a role in determining which non-pharmaceutical methods were employed.

Overall, the findings underscore the value of a holistic approach to pain management that incorporates both the clinical and personal preferences of patients and nurses. By addressing these influencing factors and enhancing training opportunities, healthcare institutions can better support nurses in delivering comprehensive pain management care that goes beyond medication alone.

5.5 Conclusion

This study underscores the importance of non-pharmacological interventions as integral components of patient-centered pain management in nursing practice. The findings reveal that a majority of nurses employ a diverse range of techniques, such as reassurance, massage, patient education, and physical adjustments, all of which play a crucial role in managing patient pain and enhancing comfort. However, institutional policies, workload, time constraints, and training availability significantly influence the implementation of these methods.

The study highlights the necessity for healthcare institutions to provide robust support, clear policies, and specialized training to enable nurses to effectively use non-pharmacological interventions. This approach can improve patient care, foster holistic pain management practices,

and enhance nurse-patient interactions by addressing pain through both clinical and non-clinical means. With targeted strategies to address the identified barriers, nurses can better integrate these essential methods into routine care, ultimately improving the quality of pain management and patient satisfaction.

5.6 Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the use and effectiveness of non-pharmacological pain management techniques in nursing practice:

- **Enhance Training and Continuing Education:** Healthcare institutions should offer regular training sessions and workshops focused on non-pharmacological pain management techniques. Evidence shows that nurses with specialized training are more likely to incorporate these interventions effectively, suggesting that ongoing education can increase proficiency and confidence in using various methods.
- **Implement Supportive Institutional Policies:** Hospitals and clinics should establish policies that support the use of non-pharmacological interventions alongside standard care. By formalizing these techniques within institutional protocols, nurses may feel encouraged and empowered to utilize a wider range of strategies to address patient pain.
- **Address Workload and Time Constraints:** To improve the implementation of non-pharmacological methods, healthcare facilities should consider staffing adjustments to reduce nurse-to-patient ratios. This would allow nurses the time needed to offer more individualized, non-pharmacological pain management without compromising other aspects of patient care.

- **Promote Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Encourage collaboration among healthcare providers, including physical therapists, occupational therapists, and pain management specialists, to create comprehensive, multidisciplinary pain management plans. This collaboration can provide patients with diverse coping strategies and reinforce the use of non-pharmacological measures.
- **Encourage Patient and Family Involvement:** Since family support plays a significant role in managing pain, healthcare facilities should facilitate patient-family engagement in the care process. Providing education for families on non-pharmacological pain relief methods can improve patients' comfort and encourage a supportive healing environment.
- **Allocate Resources for Equipment and Comfort Devices:** Facilities should ensure availability of essential comfort devices, such as pillows, hot/cold packs, and specialized mattresses, to enable nurses to apply these methods consistently. Having access to these resources will make it easier for nurses to offer a range of non-pharmacological options.
- **Conduct Further Research and Feedback Assessments:** Regular assessments of nurses' usage of non-pharmacological pain management techniques and gathering patient feedback on their efficacy can provide data to refine and enhance these practices continuously.

By addressing these recommendations, healthcare facilities can create an environment that supports and empowers nurses to deliver effective, holistic pain management.

5.7 Suggestions for further Studies

Future studies should explore various dimensions of non-pharmacological pain management to deepen understanding and support broader implementation in nursing practice. The following suggestions highlight key areas for further research:

- **Evaluating the Long-term Efficacy of Non-Pharmacological Techniques:** Investigating the long-term effectiveness of specific non-pharmacological methods, such as deep breathing, massage, and hot/cold therapy, across different patient demographics and conditions would provide valuable insights into the sustained benefits of these interventions.
- **Impact of Training Programs on Technique Proficiency:** Studies assessing how specialized training programs influence nurses' proficiency and confidence in using non-pharmacological techniques would help identify best practices for educational approaches in this area. Additionally, research could explore how the frequency and type of training impact nurses' ability to implement these methods effectively.

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APPENDIX
QUESTIONNAIRE

DEPARTMENT OF NURSINGSCIENCE
SCHOOL OF BASICMEDICAL SCIENCES
UNIVERSITYOF BENIN, BENINCITY, EDOSTATE

Dear Respondent,

I am Emuobor Godgift Okeoghene ;a 500L student in the above named institution. I am carrying out a research study on the topic: “The Use of Nonpharmacological Measures by Nurses In The Relief Of Patients’ Pain in a Tertiary Health Institution” . Kindly assist me by indicating your opinion where necessary. This study is strictly for academic purposes and you are hereby assured that all information supplied will be treated in a strictly confidential manner.

Thank you.

Yours faithfully,

Emuobor Godgift Okeoghene

Instruction: Tick the appropriate box in each section below

SECTIONA: DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

1. Age: (a) 21-30yrs(), (b) 31-40 (), (c) 41-50 (), (d) 51andabove()
2. Marital Status: (a) Single(), (b) Married(), (c) Divorced()
3. Educational background:
(a) Ond [] (b) Hnd [] (c) BNSc [] (d) MSN [] (e) DNP [] (f) Others
(specify)_____
4. Religion: (a) Christian(), (b) Muslim(), (c) pagan(), (d) Others
Specify.....
5. Specify your designation: (a) NO11(), (b) NO1(), (c) SNO(), (d) PNO() , € ACNO(),
(f) CNO(), (g) ADNS ()
6. Years of working experience (a) 0-5yrs(), (b) 6-10yrs(), (c) 11-15yrs(), (d) 16-
20yrs() € 21-25yrs(), (f) 26yrsandabove()
7. What is the highest educational qualification you attained in nursing?(a) Bachelor Degree
(B.Sc.) (), (b) Master(), (c) Ph.D. (), € Others.....
8. What is your professional qualification(a) RN(), (b) RM(), (c) RNM(), € RPN(), (f)
RPN(), (g) RAEN(), (h) others.....
9. Any special training in non pharmacological pain relief techniques(specify) _____

SECTION B: DIFFERENT TYPES OF NONPHARMACOLOGICAL MEASURES UTILIZED BY NURSES IN PATIENTS' PAIN RELIEF IN UBTH

Please indicate by ticking the appropriate box (Yes Or No), the type of Nonpharmacological Pain relief techniques that you utilize in your practice:

10. Massage: Yes() No(). 11. Hot/Cold compress: Yes() No(). 12. Distraction techniques: Yes() No(). 13. Reassurance and emotional support : Yes() No(). 14. Deep breathing technique: Yes() No(). 15. Repositioning of patients : Yes() No(). 16. Reading of Bible, Quran or other spiritual/religious practices such as prayers: Yes() No(). 17. Presence of family and loved ones around my patients during pain: Yes() No(). 18. Simple comfort devices such as pillows, special mattress, air rings amongst others: Yes() No(). 19. Patient education and counseling: Yes() No(). 20. Limiting patients' movements to reduce pain : Yes() No().

Others(specify): _____

SECTION C: NURSES' FREQUENCY OF UTILIZATION OF NON-PHARMACOLOGICAL MEASURES OF PAIN RELIEF

SN	Measure Utilized	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Not at all
21.	Massage					
22.	Hot/Cold					
23.	Distraction techniques					
24.	Reassurance and emotional support					
25..	Deep breathing technique					
26.	Repositioning of patients					
27.	Reading of Bible, Quran or other spiritual/religious practices such as prayers					
28.	Presence of family and loved ones around my patients during pain					
29.	Simple comfort devices such as pillows, special mattress, air rings amongst others					
30.	Patient education and counseling					
31.	Limiting patients' movements to reduce pain					

SECTIOND: FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CHOICES OF NON-PHARMACOLOGICAL INTERVENTIONS UTILIZED BY NURSES IN PAIN RELIEF.

- 32. Time constraint: Yes() No().
- 33. Lack of necessary equipment: Yes() No().
- 34. Special training in non pharmacological pain relief measures: Yes() No().
- 35. Heavy workload on nurses : Yes() No().
- 36. Beliefs of the patient : Yes() No().
- 37. Beliefs of the nurse : Yes() No().
- 38. Personal preferences of the patient : Yes() No().
- 39. Healthcare institution policy and practices: Yes() No().

APPENDIX II

RELIABILITY OF INSTRUMENT (QUESTIONNAIRE) OF NURSES' UTILIZATION OF NON PHARMACOLOGICAL MEASURES OF PAIN RELIEF IN THE UNIVERSITY OF BENIN BENIN TEACHING HOSPITAL, BENIN CITY, EDO STATE.

A pilot study was conducted using 10% of the target population in the University of Benin Teaching Hospital, to test the reliability of the instrument, lapses in the instrument were identified, amended and the needed corrections and adjustments were made thereby making the instrument reliable.

Variables	Number of items	Cronbach's Alpha
Different types of non pharmacological measures used by nurses	11	0.85
Frequency of utilization of non pharmacological measures by nurses	11	0.8
Factors influencing nurses' utilization of non pharmacological measures of pain relief	8	0.75

The reliability of the questionnaire was determined using the Cronbach Alpha with results indicating a high consistency : Different types of non pharmacological measures used by nurses ($\alpha = 0.85$), Frequency of utilization of non pharmacological measures by nurses ($\alpha = 0.8$) and Factors influencing nurses' utilization of non pharmacological measures in pain relief ($\alpha = 0.75$) thereby confirming the instrument is reliable for this study.